

Review

Beyond Haemostasis and Thrombosis: Platelets in Depression and Its Co-Morbidities

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Abstract: Alongside their function in primary haemostasis and thrombo-inflammation, platelets are increasingly considered a bridge between mental, immunological and coagulation-related disorders. This review focuses on the link between platelets and the pathophysiology of major depressive disorder (MDD) and its most frequent comorbidities. Platelet- and neuron-shared proteins involved in MDD are functionally described. Platelet-related studies performed in the context of MDD, cardiovascular disease, and major neurodegenerative, neuropsychiatric and neurodevelopmental disorders are transversally presented from an epidemiological, genetic and functional point of view. To provide a complete scenario, we report the analysis of original data on the epidemiological link between platelets and depression symptoms suggesting moderating and interactive effects of sex on this association. Epidemiological and genetic studies discussed suggest that blood platelets might also be relevant biomarkers of MDD prediction and occurrence in the context of MDD comorbidities. Finally, this review has the ambition to formulate some directives and perspectives for future research on this topic.

Keywords: depression; platelets; cardiovascular disease; psychiatric comorbidities; neurodegenerative disorders; platelet distribution width; gender

1. Introduction

Platelets are increasingly considered a putative bridge linking mental, immunological, and coagulation-related disorders, alongside their function in primary haemostasis and thrombo-inflammation. Patients with complex neurological and neuropsychiatric disorders such as schizophrenia, Parkinson and Alzheimer's diseases have already been described with altered platelet function several decades ago [1–6]. Since then, numerous studies have given better insight into those early observations, by deciphering the cellular, molecular and functional similarities between platelets and neurons [7–11], and they have set the basis for the use of blood platelets as a working model to study several neurological diseases [3,8,9,12–16].

Platelets not only mirror neurons in several aspects, but directly contribute to the pathophysiology of those diseases affecting them in several ways. We will focus on the link between platelets and the pathophysiology of major depressive disorder (MDD), one of the leading causes of the

disability and disease burden worldwide. MDD presents as a persistent low mood, with associated changes in behavior, cognition, sleep and appetite, impaired social and occupational functioning, increased risk of self-harm or suicide [17,18]. MDD is also associated with increased mortality due to several comorbidities, especially cardiovascular disease (CVD). Moreover, depression shows a high comorbidity with many other disabling conditions, including neurodegenerative, neuropsychiatric and neurodevelopmental disorders. With this review we first aim at providing functional evidence for a platelet pathophysiological involvement in depression by highlighting the intrinsic platelet characteristics in drug-free depressed patients. Additionally, we present here an overview of the current state of the art in epidemiological and genetic studies linking MDD and its main co-morbidities with platelets, in addition to providing some original data on the epidemiological link between platelet parameters and depression symptoms.

2. Platelet “Bridge” Proteins Linking Thrombosis and Inflammation with Depression

Despite their different embryonic origin [15,19], platelets and neurons share several characteristics. Platelets mimic the stable synaptic structure between neurons, i.e., where they interact with each other [4]. With neurons, they share the complex molecular machinery that regulates granule trafficking [7], controlling the calcium-dependent release reaction of stored agonists, after activation stimulation in platelets and the neurotransmitter release following an action potential in neurons [20]; they both have similar secretory vesicles in terms of content, storing molecules such as serotonin or 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT), dopamine, epinephrine, glutamate, gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), calcium, adenosine 5'-diphosphate (ADP) and Adenosine 5'-triphosphate (ATP). Platelets and neurons also share a number of proteins that include serotonin transporters and receptors [8,19,20] as well as some markers originally known as neuron-specific such as reelin, amyloid precursor protein (APP) and brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) [10,21,22].

Several studies have identified an association of the (epi)genetic variability of genes encoding some of the key players in depression etiology with both mood disorders and thrombo-inflammatory conditions such as CVD. Those studies have been inspired by the functional role that neuron- and platelet- shared proteins have in platelets themselves. In many instances, these genes encode shared proteins between neurons and platelets including the serotonergic pathway, cannabinoid receptor 1 and *BDNF* [23–28]. *BDNF* is probably the most studied of them as one of its specific variants (Val66Met, G to A, rs6265) has been consistently reported to influence the predisposition to CVD associated with depression [25,27,29]. Although (epi)genetic studies identifying novel genes with pleiotropic effects on both platelets and neurons in the context of depression are missing, there is increasing functional evidence that links some of these proteins to both depression and thrombo-inflammation. In this section of the review, we will go over this evidence by describing the role of four of the most relevant platelet proteins involved in platelet function and depression.

2.1. Serotonin (5-HT)

Discovered in 1935 by the Italian pharmacologist Vittorio Erspamer [30], 5-HT is a monoamine neurotransmitter implicated in numerous neuropsychological processes [31], including the pathophysiology of MDD [32,33]. Owing to the role of serotonin in platelets, the idea was born to use platelets as an experimental system for neurons [34–36], stemming from the observation of its specific uptake by platelets and from its release mechanisms and pharmacological regulation in animal models [37–41]. Several studies have subsequently confirmed that platelets are an adequate model of serotonin storage and release from serotonergic neurons, under both physiological and pathological conditions [32,34–36,42,43]. Platelets are the main serotonin reservoir in the bloodstream [44] resembling its vesicular storage in neurons [45]. Taken up from the circulating blood via the serotonin transporter (SERT or SLC6A4) [46–50], serotonin is stored in dense granules via the vesicular monoamine transporter 2 (VMAT2 or SLC18A2) [6,51,52] from where it can be released after platelet stimulation [53,54] to take part in platelet activation and acute inflammatory responses. Platelets express the serotonin

receptors 2A (5-HT_{2A}) and 3A (5-HT_{3A}): platelet binding of serotonin activates PLC β leading to intracellular Ca²⁺ release that stabilizes platelet activation. Autocrine serotonin signaling therefore contributes to platelet integrin α IIb/ β 3 activation and to an increased surface expression of P-selectin [55]. Important similarities have been observed between 5-HT_{2A} receptor characteristics [56–58] or SERT structure [59] in the brain cortex and in platelets. These similarities have led to a handful of studies in platelets of depressed patients with or without other co-morbidities, mainly focusing on serotonin metabolism. Depressed patients showed up-regulation of the 5-HT receptor, decreased serotonin transporter binding, and decreased rate of 5-HT uptake [60]. Increased density of the 5-HT_{2A} receptor has been detected in platelets of depressed suicide victims [61–63]. In depressed patients, SERT showed a decreased number of serotonin binding sites [33,64,65], and a decreased platelet SERT maximal velocity [66]. SERT serotonin transport was found to be enhanced in patients with depression [67] and was identified as the main pharmacological target of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), which prevent serotonin uptake in platelets [59].

More recently, the modulation of innate and adaptive immunity by platelet serotonin has been implicated in the regulation of inflammation [68–72]. The latter is also supported by the evidence that 5-HT receptors are expressed on numerous inflammatory cells besides platelets [73]. Platelet 5-HT is able to regulate both P- and E-selectin expression on murine endothelial cells, thereby influencing important inflammatory processes such as the rolling and adhesion of neutrophils [74–78].

2.2. Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor (BDNF)

BDNF is a secretory protein regulating the development and function of neural circuits [79–81], expressed in both central and peripheral nervous systems [82]. Despite also being expressed in a number of peripheral tissues and cell types, platelets are the main source and storage cell of peripheral BDNF, representing 90% of total blood BDNF [22,83–85]. In line with this evidence, the *platelet count* (Plt) appears to be the factor that is most associated with serum BDNF concentrations [86,87]. BDNF is expressed and stored in human megakaryocyte α -granules together with platelet factor 4 (PF4) [88] and is released by platelets at the site of injury during platelet aggregation [85,89,90], impacting thrombosis [88,91]. This process occurs through activation of the protease-activated receptor 1 (PAR1) during thrombin stimulation [92]. Interestingly, BDNF stored in platelets not only derives from megakaryocytes, but also from cells in the brain and other organs that can, therefore, modulate BDNF levels in the circulation [89].

Altered BDNF levels have been found in patients with depression [93,94] and its co-morbidities [95–97]. Platelet granules containing BDNF were decreased in MDD [98,99]. Moreover, while about half of the BDNF platelet content is released upon platelet activation [83], some evidence suggests that in depressed patients the release of BDNF seems to be independent of platelet reactivity [84].

2.3. Reelin

Reelin is a neuronal protein regulating brain development, synaptic plasticity and memory formation [100–102]. It is not only expressed in the central nervous system, but also in a number of peripheral organs and in blood [103]. On the one hand, reelin is able to foster vascular inflammation via leukocyte–endothelial adhesion, thereby promoting atherosclerosis [104]. On the other hand, it upregulates thrombin generation and the formation of fibrin clots leading to blood coagulation [105]. Reelin can also be actively released following platelet activation thereby inducing Akt, Erk, Syk, and 1-phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2 (PLC γ 2) activation through its contact with glycoprotein Ib (GPIb), the APP and the ApoER2 receptor [106]. It also supports platelet binding to collagen and glycoprotein VI (GPVI)-dependent RAC1 activation, PLC γ 2 phosphorylation, platelet activation and aggregation [107], and it is a positive regulator of platelet spreading on fibrinogen [108].

2.4. Amyloid β Peptides ($A\beta$ Peptides)

$A\beta$ peptide overproduction is a common feature of both Alzheimer's disease and chronic central nervous system diseases including depression [109–112]. At the same time, $A\beta$ peptides are strongly proinflammatory, proapoptotic, and proatherogenic molecules with $A\beta$ 1-40 being abundantly expressed in endothelial cells [113], vascular smooth muscle cells [114], macrophages [115], monocytes and platelets [113,116,117].

$A\beta$ peptides are proteolytic fragments of APP, an integral membrane protein [118,119]. The *APP* gene produces 3 major splice variants, with the APP770 being specifically expressed in megakaryocytes and platelets [120,121]. In platelets, APP is stored in α -granules from where it is released upon platelet activation. On the one hand, released APP is able to participate in haemostasis by influencing coagulation, thrombosis and bleeding [122–126]. On the other hand, amyloid $A\beta$ peptides can trigger platelet activation, adhesion and aggregation [21] through a number of different pathways: they can interact with CD36 and GP1b α and activate p38 MAPK/COX1 pathways, leading to thromboxane A₂ (TxA₂) release [127]; they can bind to integrin α IIb β 3 and trigger the release of ADP [128]; they are able to bind the PAR1 thrombin receptor and stimulate Ras/Raf, PI3K, P38MAPK, and cPLA2 and TxA₂ formation and release [129]; they can act as ligand for the platelet activation receptor GPVI [130]; they can induce protein kinase C (PKC) activation and tyrosine phosphorylation through a NOX-dependent pathway [131]; they may cause platelet shape change and granule release through activation of the small GTPase RhoA and phosphorylation of myosin light chain kinase leading to cytoskeletal reorganization [21]. There is some evidence that the amyloidogenic pathway is also regulated at the post-transcriptional level by a number of platelet miRNAs including the ones regulating fibrinogen [132], the β site APP cleaving enzyme 1 (*BACE1*) and APP expression [133].

Few studies performed on both human and mouse platelets, have shown that anti-platelet treatments, such as clopidogrel and aspirin, are able to interfere with APP/ $A\beta$ peptide generation and function in platelets and/or neurons [128,134–136].

3. MDD and Platelets: Further Evidence of a Link

3.1. Epidemiological Studies

The relation between platelets and depression has been deeply investigated, both through epidemiological and—less often—through statistical genetics approaches. Some studies reported increased platelet activation in individuals with depression, compared to healthy controls. Musselman et al. observed an enhanced baseline platelet activation and responsiveness in patients affected by MDD, as suggested by the increased expression of platelet α IIb β 3 and P-selectin [137], while Pinto and colleagues [138] demonstrated an impairment of L-arginine-nitric oxide signaling in platelets of depressed compared to healthy subjects. Morel-Kopp et al. [139] reported a direct association of MDD with a higher number of CD62- and CD63-positive platelets and excitability, which were attenuated by a 6-month treatment with anti-depressants, in line with previous findings on platelet secretion in response to collagen binding [140]. An increased oxidative stress and hyperaggregability were observed in platelets of MDD cases compared to controls [141], as well as a higher content of serotonin, interleukin 1 β , PF4 and CD40 ligand (CD40L) [142]. In line with this evidence, a recent longitudinal study on young males reported mental stress to be associated with increased and prolonged proinflammatory platelet bioactivity: while exposure to chronic stress led to an increased number of CD63⁺ platelets, acute stress was associated with alterations of CD62P⁺, CD63⁺, PAC-1⁺ platelets and of platelet-leukocyte aggregates [143].

Other epidemiological studies investigated the relation between MDD and platelets by making use of platelet parameters commonly tested, like mean platelet volume (MPV) and Plt. A positive association between MPV and MDD was reported in a Turkish population sample (N = 2286, 287 cases) [144], and later replicated in a study comparing 103 MDD patients and 106 controls [145], as well as in a hospital-based study (90 cases vs. 49 controls) [146]. However, these studies revealed contrasting

evidence of association between Plt and MDD status: while Bondade and colleagues observed an increased Plt in depressed patients [146], Cai et al. found no statistical evidence supporting that finding [145]. They reported a positive association between MDD and plateletcrit (PCT), i.e., the product of MPV and Plt, which represents the total mass occupied by platelets in the blood [145]. Platelet parameters have also been studied with reference to MDD treatments: in a small study comparing 15 MDD patients under escitalopram therapy—one of the most used SSRI treatments—and 17 healthy controls, treated patients exhibited a significant reduction in both MPV and Plt, which were instead higher than in controls at baseline [147]. Another study comparing 31 patients with life-long recurrent depression treated with SSRIs and 31 matched healthy controls, reported significantly higher MPV, platelet distribution width (PDW, an index of size variability of circulating platelets) and platelet-to-larger cell ratio (P-LCR; i.e., the proportion of large platelets with volume >12 fL, which represents an index of platelet size useful in the diagnosis of thrombocytopenia) in depressed participants [148]. Although a direct link between PDW variability and platelet function has not yet been fully established [149], this evidence suggests once again that lower platelet activation and function may be a feature of depression, along with lower platelet and blood plasma serotonin, and lower platelet reactivity. Moreover, studies on collagen- and epinephrine-induced aggregation and the percentage of spiny and discoid platelets also suggested a lower platelet reactivity as a potential feature of depression [148]. In line with this evidence, in a comprehensive analysis of the relation between low-grade inflammation and mental health in a large Italian population cohort (the Moli-sani study; N = 12,732), our group identified a significant positive association between continuous depressive symptoms and PDW [150]. This association survived conservative adjustments for several sociodemographic, health and lifestyle covariates, suggesting the existence of shared genetic underpinnings between depressive status and platelet size variability [150].

3.2. Genomic Studies

The epidemiological findings reported above represent a robust rationale to investigate the shared basis between depression risk and platelet variability also at the genetic level. In a large genome-wide association study (GWAS) of blood cell measures ($N_{\max} \sim 170,000$) [151], the authors performed a multivariable Mendelian randomization (MR) analysis on platelet parameters and MDD risk, so as to investigate potential causative effects of the former—assumed as exposure—on the latter, taken as an outcome (see [152–155] for overviews on MR rationale, assumptions and techniques). This revealed no significant causal effect of platelet parameters on MDD, although MPV and PDW showed marginally significant effects, which in any case did not survive correction for multiple testing [151]. More recently, Wray et al. reported a large GWAS on depression, with 135,458 cases and 344,901 controls, identifying 44 independent loci associated with MDD risk [156]. The authors performed genetic correlation analyses to investigate significant genetic overlaps—better defined as single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)-based co-heritability [157,158]—between MDD risk and other different disorders and traits, including Plt and MPV. They observed no significant genetic correlations between depression and platelet parameters [156]. Following these studies, we recently revisited the link between platelet parameters and MDD risk using summary statistics from these two studies, combining genetic correlation and MR analysis [149]. Beyond using GWAS summary statistics of platelet parameters from a sample size much larger than the one used before ($\sim 166,000$ vs. $\sim 67,000$ participants) [151,159], for the first time we investigated PDW in relation to MDD risk at the genetic level, reporting a significant positive genetic correlation between the two traits [149]. However, MR analyses revealed no evidence of a causal relationship between PDW and MDD, probably due to the low number of instrumental variants overlapping between the two studies; further investigations are warranted in this perspective, using summary statistics from even larger GWAS as they become available. In spite of the interesting co-heritability between PDW variability and MDD risk at the genomic level, the specific genes and variants at its basis need to be elucidated, and dedicated efforts are under way for this purpose.

4. Sex and Its Neglected Role in the Common Soil between Depression and Platelet Pathophysiology

Sex effect on the platelet-MDD association has been largely neglected in previous studies [144–146]. To this end and for the purpose of this review, we made use of the Moli-sani cohort to investigate the influence of sex on the link between depression and platelet indices. Specifically, we performed generalized linear models (glm) using depressive symptoms (standardized PHQ9-6 scale) as outcome and platelet parameters (standardized Plt, MPV and PDW) as exposures—stratified by gender, adjusted for age, lifestyles and chronic prevalent conditions, as in Gialluisi et al. [150]. Associations in women were further adjusted for variables potentially influencing hormonal status such as current menopause status, use of oral contraceptives and use of hormonal replacement therapy, so as to avoid potential confounding effects [160–162]. Moreover, we carried out a glm in the total sample (N = 12,732) [150], further adjusted for sex and including an interaction term with the latter factor, for each of the platelet parameters tested. This original analysis (reported in Table 1) revealed a substantial lack of association of Plt with depressive symptoms in both sexes, while MPV showed a significant negative association, but only in women. Interestingly, a positive association of PDW with depressive symptoms was present in both groups, with the effect size in women being two-fold higher than in men. However, in the total sample, we observed no significant interaction effect of PWD and sex on depressive symptoms. Of note, while potential confounders modifying hormonal status in women did not affect associations between platelet parameters and depressive symptoms within the Moli-sani study, sex hormones may still play a role in this association and further systematic analyses are warranted to rule out a potential influence of these variables, when hormone titers will be available within the cohort.

Table 1. Influence of sex on the association between platelet parameters and depression.

Platelet Parameter	Effect	Beta	SE	P	Setting (N)
Plt	Plt only	0.004	0.013	0.77	Women (6421)
	Plt + hormone-related variables ^a	0.005	0.013	0.70	
	Plt only	−0.008	0.011	0.48	Men (6311)
	Interactive (Plt-by-sex)	0.018	0.017	0.30	ALL (12,732)
MPV	MPV only	−0.034	0.014	0.01	Women (6421)
	MPV + hormone-related variables ^a	−0.034	0.014	0.01	
	MPV only	−0.015	0.011	0.16	Men (6311)
	Interactive (MPV-by-sex)	−0.025	0.017	0.14	ALL (12,732)
PDW	PDW only	0.046	0.014	1 × 10^{−3}	Women (6421)
	PDW + hormone-related variables ^a	0.048	0.014	6 × 10^{−4}	
	PDW only	0.021	0.010	0.04	Men (6311)
	Interactive (PDW-by-sex)	0.029	0.017	0.09	ALL (12,732)

Sex-stratified associations between common platelet parameters (platelet count (Plt), mean platelet volume (MPV), platelet distribution width (PDW)) and depressive symptoms (PHQ9-6) and sex-by-platelet interaction analysis in the Moli-sani cohort. ^a Associations further adjusted for binary variables (yes/no) specifying current menopause status, use of oral contraceptives and of hormonal replacement therapy in women. Significant associations are reported in bold.

5. MDD Comorbidities and Platelets

Depression and depressive symptoms are frequently comorbid with cardiovascular disease, neurodegenerative, neuropsychiatric and neurodevelopmental disorders [163]. The latter have important clinical implications since depression may dramatically contribute to worsen those diseases and in general have an impact on overall health [164]. Indeed, comorbid depression has been associated with worse prognosis and increased mortality [165,166] and with a higher risk of developing other diseases later in life [167]. Several mechanisms have been proposed to explain the co-occurrence of depression with the comorbidities mentioned above, including treatment-induced morbidity, behavioral and psychological factors, but also underlying biological processes [163]. In this section, we will review the studies showing the implication of blood platelets as a possible common underlying marker of depression in comorbidity with cardiovascular disease and in major neurodegenerative, neuropsychiatric and neurodevelopmental disorders. A summary of shared associated platelet markers among MDD and its comorbidities is reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Overview of shared platelet biomarkers across major depressive disorder (MDD) and its comorbidities.

Platelet Parameter	Depression Related Clinical Phenotype
Plt	<p>↑ in MDD [146], PanDis [168,169], GAD [146], ASD [170], ADHD [171,172]</p> <p>↓ in GAD [173]</p> <p>No association with MDD [145], Depressive Symptoms with MI [174], AD [175], PD [175,176], PanDis [177,178], ADHD [171,172,179,180]</p>
MPV	<p>↑ in MDD [144–147], Depressive Symptoms [150], post-Ischemic Stroke depression [181,182], AD [175,183], PD [175], PanDis [177,184,185], GAD [146,173], ADHD [171,179,180,186]</p> <p>↓ in VaD patients [187] and in AD [187,188], MCI [188], PanDis [168,169,178]</p> <p>Negative correlation with PD progression stage (Hoehn and Yahr score [175,176]),</p> <p>Positive association with cognitive performance (MMSE) [187,188] although no correlation was reported elsewhere [175]</p>
PDW	<p>↑ in Depressive symptoms [150], PanDis [168,169,185], ADHD [171]</p> <p>↓ in VaD patients [187], AD [183,187,188], MCI [188]</p> <p>No association with PanDis [178], GAD [173]</p>
PCT	<p>↑ in MDD [145], ADHD [171,172,179,180,186]</p> <p>No association with GAD [173]</p>
Platelet serotonin metabolism	<p>↑ platelet serotonin receptor in MDD [189,190], Depressed CVD patients [191]</p> <p>↓ platelet serotonin transporter in MDD [192]</p> <p>↑ platelet serotonin uptake in AD [193]</p> <p>↓ platelet serotonin uptake in AD [194–196]</p> <p>No alteration in AD [197,198]</p> <p>↑ platelet serotonin levels in post-MI depressed patients [199] and Dementia [200]</p> <p>↓ platelet serotonin levels in AD [201–203] and ALS [204]</p>
Platelet mitochondria parameters	<p>↑ MAO-B activity in PD [205–208]</p> <p>↓ MAO-B activity in late phase AD [202]</p> <p>No alteration of MAO-B activity in PD [209,210]</p> <p>↓ mitochondrial Complex I activity in PD [211–213]</p> <p>No alteration of mitochondrial Complex I activity in PD [214,215]</p> <p>abnormal platelet mitochondrial morphology in ALS [216]</p>
Platelet activation markers	<p>↑ P-selectin in MDD [137,139], acute stress [143], AD [217]</p> <p>↑ platelet-leukocyte aggregates in acute stress [143], AD [217]</p> <p>↑ CD63+ platelets in MDD [139], chronic and acute stress [143]</p> <p>↑ PF4 and βTG in depressed CAD patients [218–221]</p>

The studies reporting antidepressant drug-treated patients were excluded. ↑: increased or positive association; ↓: decreased or negative association. Plt: platelet count; MPV: mean platelet volume; PDW: platelet distribution width; PCT: plateletcrit. MAO-B: monoamine oxidase B; PF4: platelet factor 4; βTG: β-thromboglobulin. MDD: major depressive disorder, PanDis: panic disorder, GAD: generalized anxiety disorder, ASD: autism spectrum disorder, ADHD: attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, MI: myocardial infarction, PD: Parkinson disease, AD: Alzheimer's disease, MCI: mild cognitive impairment, CVD: cardiovascular disease, ALS: amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, CAD: coronary artery disease.

5.1. Cardiovascular Disease

Depression and depressive symptoms have long since been established as important risk factors for cardiovascular disease related mortality. Clinical depression was identified as a significant risk factor for mortality in patients with coronary heart disease (CHD) [222] or myocardial infarction (MI) [223], and in middle-aged men with stroke [224]. Patients with depression had a two- to four-fold higher risk of death after a cardiac event [225,226], and showed higher risk of CVD mortality between 6 and 18 months following MI [227,228]. MDD patients are also at a higher risk of dying after a congestive heart failure (CHF) [229,230] and they have an increased CVD morbidity [225]. In patients with an acute MI, depression was found to be a risk factor for cardiac mortality independent of cardiac disease severity [231,232], and was associated with an increased risk of death in young women with coronary artery disease (CAD) [233]. In another study, depressed patients showed a 77% increased risk of all-cause mortality, 10 years after percutaneous coronary intervention [234]. A direct relationship between depressive symptoms and all-cause mortality was also found in the Framingham Heart Study [235] and in the Moli-sani [236] cohorts.

Clinical depression was not only associated with CVD and all-cause mortality, but was also shown in numerous reports to be a leading risk factor for CVD occurrence. Several studies published over the last 30 years have additionally indicated a bidirectional co-morbidity between MDD and CVD occurrence. In a meta-analysis of 124,509 individuals across 21 studies Nicholson and colleagues identified an 80% increased risk for developing coronary artery disease in association with depression [237]. Depressed patients had a two- to four-fold risk of developing CVD at some point in their lifetime [238–243], and different epidemiological studies have highlighted that patients suffering from ischemic heart disease show a high incidence of depression [244–247]. On the one hand, MDD was also associated with an increased risk of developing stroke (Hazard Ratio 1.45) [248]; on the other hand, 30% of stroke survivors developed MDD according to two meta-analyses [249,250]. Therefore, a bidirectional causality link between these disorders has been hypothesized. Comorbidity between depression and cardio-metabolic traits has been reported in a number of studies [251].

Beside potential behavioral explanations for this increased risk such as medication noncompliance, cigarette smoking and physical inactivity, other biological factors including a proinflammatory state, endothelial dysfunction and/or platelet activation have been considered [242,252,253]. Increasing evidence has pointed to a specific role for platelets in influencing the CVD-MDD comorbidity [254–256]. First of all, a higher platelet aggregability has been considered as a marker of patients with both CVD and MDD, as platelet hyperactivity could explain both pathological phenotypes [255,257]. As highlighted previously, higher platelet aggregability is a signature of depressed patients without cardiovascular events. Depressed patients display increased platelet serotonin receptor concentrations [189,190] and abnormally low platelet SERT levels [192] which would result in elevated serotonin concentration in the bloodstream. This would in turn lead to abnormal platelet aggregation in atherosclerotic arteries [258,259]. Indeed, elevated blood levels of serotonin are predictive of CAD and ischemic cardiac events in patients with suspected CAD [260], and in vitro experiments have demonstrated higher platelet aggregability in CVD/MDD patients [199,218,219,261]. In addition to that, post-myocardial depressed patients showed abnormal whole blood and platelet serotonin levels [199], and depressed CVD patients have a higher serotonin receptor density [191]. Anxiety, often accompanying depression (see below), has been shown to be a predictor of adrenaline and serotonin-dependent platelet reactivity in CAD patients [262]. All these findings were supported by the evidence that an SSRI-treatment decreased platelet aggregation and activity in CAD patients [263,264], and they led to several clinical trials to evaluate the health effects of SSRIs versus placebo or no antidepressants in patients with CHD and depression [265].

Because higher platelet aggregability was not always a consistent finding in patients with the MDD/CVD comorbidity [254,266,267], other studies have instead focused on measuring platelet activity by means of platelet activation markers or metabolization. Some studies have looked at PF4 and β -thromboglobulin (β -TG) levels in depressed patients with or without CAD [218–221] or alternatively

in cerebrovascular disease [268] and non-depressed matched controls. In general, both PF4 and β -TG were higher in depressed compared to non-depressed CAD patients [218–220], as well as in depressed CAD patients compared to CAD- and depression-free controls [221]. In a recent study [269], the activity of platelet-dependent NAD and NADP dehydrogenases has been measured as read-out of platelet metabolism in patients with acute coronary syndrome (ACS) with or without concomitant anxiety-depressive disorder (ADD) followed up for one year for recurrent cardiovascular complications. Among the patients that developed cardiovascular complications over the follow-up period, the ones with the concomitant ACS and ADD had lower NADP-MDH activity compared to controls and to ACS patients without ADD [269].

Very few studies have tried to investigate whether platelet indices (among several markers) represent good risk factors or markers of MDD and CVD comorbidity. Increased PLR and MPV were shown to be predictive biomarkers of the development of post-stroke depression in acute ischemic stroke patients [181,182,270]. Except for one study where no significant association was found between Plt and somatic and cognitive depression symptoms concomitant with MI [174], other similar reports focusing on platelet indices and CVD comorbidities of depression are lacking.

5.2. Neurodegenerative Diseases

Common neurodegenerative diseases linked to the accumulation of neurotoxic protein aggregates are usually diagnosed when the disease is already at an advanced stage of neurodegeneration [12,271]. This makes it very important to identify potential biomarkers that are easy to measure and that could predict the incident risk of these disorders, e.g., as circulating biomarkers [272]. Platelets are, in different ways, associated with the pathophysiology of neurodegenerative disorders. First, they have a crucial role in the metabolism and storage of dopamine, A β peptides and APP [10], as previously discussed. This led the way to a handful of functional platelet studies briefly reviewed here below (most relevant human studies) and more extensively elsewhere [273]. More recently, the link between neurodegenerative disorders and classical blood platelet parameters like MPV, Plt and PDW has been investigated also at the epidemiological level, in a relatively limited number of studies. Indeed, platelet indices are easy-to-measure and standardized across laboratories and could be used as good prediction and/or prognosis markers of neurodegenerative risk. Based on these premises, we will focus on the most prevalent neurodegenerative disorders due to the accumulation of neurotoxic protein aggregates, i.e., Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson disease (PD) and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), reviewing epidemiological and genetic studies as well as the main functional analyses performed in cohorts of patients.

5.2.1. Alzheimer's Disease (AD)

Both functional platelet markers and platelet indices have been reported in association with AD clinical presentation.

Platelet activation markers have been investigated in AD patients in several studies, often leading to inconclusive and inconsistent findings. Higher platelet CD62P (P-selectin) expression, platelet and platelet-leukocyte mixed aggregates were found in AD patients [217]; this evidence contrasts with that of another study showing increased soluble P-selectin levels but no different CD62P expression in resting platelets, as well as lower levels in platelets stimulated by thrombin receptor activating peptide 6 (TRAP-6) [274]. In four studies by Prodan and colleagues, increased numbers of pro-coagulant protein-coated platelets were detected in early-stage AD patients compared to controls [275–278].

Contrasting evidence has been reported regarding platelet serotonin in AD patients. Lower [194–196], normal [197,198], and increased [193] platelet serotonin uptake were all shown in AD patients. Measuring intraplatelet serotonin levels also led to inconsistent findings as well [200–203]. The role of neuron and platelet serotonin in depression and AD has been further explored in a review by Meltzer et al. [279].

Based on more consistent and replicated data, the A β peptides together with monoamine oxidase B (MAO-B) have been considered as more relevant AD biomarkers in platelets [280]. The functional role of platelet A β peptides in AD has been largely investigated in animal models so that AD can be partly conceived as a thrombo-hemorrhagic disorder [281,282]. A β peptides are released at the site of vessel damage and contribute to the progression of the disease by regulating vascular amyloid deposits after platelet activation [21,123,124,283]. Several independent studies reported changes in platelet APP in AD patients [284–291].

Independent epidemiological studies have reported consistent associations between AD risk and platelet indices, in particular MPV and PDW. In a study comparing 150 Chinese vascular dementia (VaD), 110 AD patients and 150 non-demented controls, MPV and PDW were significantly lower in demented subjects and in AD, compared to vascular dementia patients [187]. Moreover, a positive correlation was observed between MPV/PDW levels and the mini-mental state examination (MMSE) score, a test commonly used to assess cognitive performance [187]. This finding was replicated in an independent Chinese study comparing AD, mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and cognitively healthy subjects (N = 120 for each group), which revealed a positive association between cognitive MMSE score, MPV and PDW. Authors also observed significantly lower MPV and PDW in AD patients vs. both MCI and control subjects, and in MCI vs. controls [188]. Another independent Chinese study of 92 AD patients and 84 age and sex-matched normal controls reported several alterations in quality and quantity of blood cells in demented patients, including a higher MPV and a lower PDW [183]. A higher MPV in AD patients was also found in a Turkish study comparing 89 AD, 93 PD patients and 104 healthy controls, although this did not correlate with MMSE performance [175]. In the same study, no significant associations were observed for Plt.

These findings suggest that platelets might have a role in AD pathology, which may also share genetic underpinnings. So far, two attempts were made to investigate this hypothesis. One used an MR analysis on platelet count (Plt), MPV, and PDW (used as exposure) vs. AD (modeled as outcome), which revealed no significant causal association [151]. However, this technique may suffer from low power since it is usually based on a low number of variants [292]. More recently, we attempted to estimate the co-heritability between these platelet parameters and AD risk based on common genetic variants, through linkage disequilibrium score regression, using information from more than one million variants in the genome and GWAS summary statistics from large genetic studies [151,293]. However, we found no evidence of significant genetic correlations for any of the platelet parameters tested. This suggests that the significant associations observed in previous epidemiological studies may be mainly due to shared environmental influence between platelet parameters and AD risk, and that common genetic influences on these traits are likely very limited, at least those of common SNPs [294].

5.2.2. Parkinson Disease (PD)

Platelet studies have been performed in the context of PD etiopathology reporting changes in the ultrastructure, mitochondrial dysfunction, increase in glutamate level and abnormal morphology [295]. However, also in the case of PD, evidence is inconsistent across studies. For example, PD platelets have been shown to have a reduced mitochondrial complex I activity [211–213] an evidence not corroborated by other studies [214,215]. Platelet MAO-B activity, the enzyme responsible for complex I inhibition in mitochondria [296], was increased in PD patients vs. controls in some reports [205–208], but was unchanged in others [209,210].

A handful of more consistent epidemiological and genetic studies investigated potential links with common platelet indices. A study comparing 80 Turkish PD patients and 80 healthy controls revealed no significant difference in Plt nor in MPV between the two groups [176]. However, MPV showed a significant negative correlation with a PD severity scale—the Hoehn and Yahr score—suggesting this could be a biomarker of PD progression in the later stages of PD [176]. In partial concordance with this finding, increased MPV has been reported in a study comparing Turkish AD and PD patients vs. controls (see above), with MPV being negatively correlated with the Hoehn and Yahr

score [175]. Of interest, PD patients showed significantly higher MPV compared to AD patients, as well, while Plt showed no significant difference across the compared groups [175]. Although some of the above-mentioned findings have been interpreted as suggestive of a link between inflammation (indicated by lower MPV) and stage of neurodegeneration (indicated by a PD progression score) [175], little is known on the pathophysiology of these disorders to make strong inferences, suggesting caution in the interpretation of these findings. Alternative hypotheses to explain the link between platelets and PD onset drew attention to mitochondrial dysfunctions in platelets, although contrasting findings have been reported on with this regard [214].

Genomic—rather than genetic—approaches to clarify this link have been attempted more recently, with the aim of investigating the presence of shared genetic underpinnings between platelet parameters and PD risk. Nalls et al. [297] tested genetic correlations between Plt/MPV and PD risk through linkage disequilibrium (LD) score regression [157,158], using summary statistics from the largest PD case–control GWAS meta-analysis carried out so far (involving ~56,300 PD cases and ~1.4 million controls), reporting no significant genetic correlations [297]. More recently, we extended this analysis to PDW and observed a significant positive genetic correlation with PD risk, suggesting the existence of a genomic overlap based on common genetic variants and indicating PDW as a new potential biomarker for PD [294]. In spite of the interesting finding, which is in line with the implication of PDW in neurodegenerative disorders [10,183,187,188] and in comorbid disorders like major depression [149], it should be noted that previous epidemiological studies reported negative associations between PDW and the risk of cognitive impairment [183,187,188], which is co-morbid and partly shares biological bases with PD [298]. At the genetic level, our group only identified a trend of (negative) correlation between PDW and AD risk [294]. Again, our limited knowledge of these disorders and of PDW itself does not currently allow us to further disentangle these aspects, although we are working towards identifying genes with pleiotropic influences on platelet variation and function and neurodegenerative risk.

5.2.3. Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS)

Another main neurodegenerative disease showing an increased risk of depression—both before and after diagnosis—is amyotrophic lateral sclerosis [299]. A further connection between the above-mentioned disorders comes from evidence implicating glutamate transmission in MDD etiology and treatment [300] and altered glutamate transportation in ALS patients [301]. For example, ALS patients show a notable reduction in high-affinity glutamate uptake in platelets, compared with normal controls and chronic neurologic disorder patients [301]. Moreover, a selective loss of glial glutamate transporter GLT-1 (EAAT2) has been reported in brain and spinal cord from sporadic ALS patients [302]. This evidence suggests a systemic impairment of platelet functionality and specifically of glutamate transport in ALS, as does the finding that platelets from ALS patients show a 37% increase in expression of glutamine synthetase [303], although in this study normal expression of the glutamate transporter EAAT2 was observed. Of interest, platelet stimulation with thrombin resulted in an approximately sevenfold increase in glutamate uptake [303]. Although data were not statistically different between ALS patients and healthy controls, this trend suggests that glutamine synthetase could represent a good peripheral marker of ALS [303]. In addition to the above-mentioned studies, both qualitative and quantitative variations in ALS platelets and platelet mitochondria have been observed, including a heterogeneous distribution of granules, formation of vacuoles, blebs, pseudopodia, as well as perturbation of mitochondrial membrane potential, mitochondrial depolarization, apoptosis and lesser intra-mitochondrial granules [216]. A recent study reported higher levels of the 43 kDa TAR DNA-binding protein (TDP-43) in platelets from sporadic ALS patients that increase with disease progression [304]. This protein is implicated in the onset of the pathology by contributing to the formation of insoluble intracellular inclusions in neurons, and is present in the majority of ALS cases [305,306].

As for classical platelet indices, we are not aware of any study investigating potential associations with ALS risk.

5.3. Neuropsychiatric and Neurodevelopmental Comorbidities of MDD

Among psychiatric comorbidities of MDD, one of the most investigated conditions with reference to platelet parameters is represented by panic disorder (PanDis). Indeed, serotonergic agents have been reported to relieve panic symptoms [307]. Some of these studies reported evidence of increased MPV in PanDis patients vs. healthy controls [177,184,185], while others reported significant associations with an opposite direction of effect [168,169,178]. Those works which analyzed PDW reported higher values for cases [168,169,185], except for one detecting no significant differences [178]. Likewise, for Plt, contrasting results were reported: higher count in PanDis patients [168,169] vs. no significant difference between cases and controls in [177,178].

Other studies have focused on generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), a related disease characterized by a persistent and chronic anxiety state. In the first (retrospective) study specifically focusing on GAD patients, these showed higher MPV and lower Plt, but no significant differences in PDW and PCT, compared to healthy controls [173]. In partial concordance with these findings, GAD patients exhibited a higher MPV and Plt, as did MDD patients, in a study comparing depressive and anxiety disorder patients vs. healthy controls in a hospital setting [146].

Patients with acute stress have been reported to have greater platelet aggregation [308,309].

Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) patients show increased platelet reactivity and aggregation in response to ADP and epinephrine stimulation [310]. A four-year longitudinal analysis of US veterans (N = 746) revealed no significant associations between Plt and the risk and course of PTSD, although Plt showed a significant association with a poorer course of depression [311].

Neuropsychiatric conditions, still, present differences in platelet parameters also when compared among themselves. Wysokiński and Szczepocka [312] compared platelet parameters like Plt, MPV and P-LCR among 2377 subjects including schizophrenia, depression, bipolar disorder and mania patients and identified several differences among these groups, for all the markers tested.

Among neurodevelopmental disorders, alterations in platelet parameters have been associated with important conditions like autism spectrum disorder (ASD) (as reviewed in [9]) and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) [171,172,186]. For ASD, anomalies have been mainly detected in platelet activation mechanisms and transport of granules [9], and a single study reported a mild increase in Plt for ASD cases and their siblings compared to controls [170]. For ADHD, although studies are still very limited, more consistent evidence of increased MPV and PCT in cases vs. control has been reported [171,172,179,180,186]. Of interest, MPV has been associated with inattention symptoms within ADHD cases, as well as with anxiety symptoms—along with Plt—in a specific subgroup of ADHD patients [172]. More recently, also significantly increased PDW in ADHD children compared to controls has been reported, beyond increased levels of Plt, MPV and PCT [171,179,180,186].

Once again, PDW presents as a novel and interesting candidate platelet biomarker for neuropsychiatric risk, although its functional and prognostic meaning remains to be elucidated.

6. Conclusions

To summarize, the independent lines of evidence reported here suggest that platelet pathophysiology has strong implications in the occurrence of MDD and of its related comorbidities (Figure 1) and they support the view that platelets reflect a circulating form of neurons [11]. However, several aspects in this fascinating hypothesis need yet to be disentangled.

First of all, the shared genetic bases between platelet variability and MDD, despite some first attempts [149,294], still needs to be elucidated through larger genetic epidemiology studies. The latter should take into account important features such as gender differences that are known to be linked to both platelet variability [313] and to the occurrence of MDD risk [314]. More studies that consider the occurrence of certain MDD comorbidities in specific population subgroups (i.e., women and pregnant women, children, aging population) are still lacking but are utterly important for further investigations.

Figure 1. Shared platelet functionality between cardiovascular and neurological disease. Activation of platelets via specific receptors, signaling cascades and degranulation allows platelets to enhance tissue inflammation and to stimulate thrombotic complications, initiating and aggravating cardiovascular malfunction. A number of specific mediators of neurological disease are also capable of influencing platelet function and platelet activation appears to be linked to the development of those neurological and psychiatric diseases, in essence attributed to brain degeneration, i.e., markers of platelet activation may reflect the stage of mental disease progress. Several of these mediators are encoded by genes whose (epi)genetic variability has been involved in both cardiovascular and mental disease. Hence, various comorbidities of cardiovascular and mental disease may occur, because of the involvement of platelets in both disorders. Therefore, commonly measured indices of platelet mass, number and their activation, which are useful to characterize platelet functionality, seem useful biomarkers of the platelet concomitant involvement in both cardiovascular and neurological disorders. Plt: platelet count, MPV: mean platelet volume, PDW: platelet distribution width, MDD: major depressive disorder, AD: Alzheimer's disease, PD: Parkinson disease, ALS: amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. Images of non-activated/activated and aggregated platelets were modified with permission from ref. [315] and [316], respectively.

Second, and related to the first point, the influence of sex on the relationship between depression risk/symptoms and platelet parameters needs to be clarified, following-up on the relevant evidence of moderate and interactive effects which we have reported here for the first time. Additional studies are warranted to verify whether the differential associations in women and men between platelet activation parameters and MDD results from intrinsic sex-specific (hormonal) differences influencing platelet activation or also from MDD-related factors.

Third, epidemiological and genetic studies increasingly identify PDW as an interesting yet functionally poorly understood candidate biomarker to test in terms of prediction of MDD and related neuropsychiatric/neurodegenerative risk in the future. The largely concordant evidence reported here that links PDW to MDD, ADHD, PanDis, as well as to cognitive traits and disorders like AD (Figure 2), is an incentive to further investigate this marker and its clinical implications. A particular topic of investigation may be its different associations and genetic correlations with PD and AD, two common neurodegenerative disorders with a partly shared biological basis.

PDW: A Novel Potential Biomarker

Figure 2. PDW: a novel potential biomarker for depression, its neurodegenerative and psychiatric comorbidities. Platelet distribution width (PDW) represents and index of platelet volume variability in a subject. It has been associated with both depressive symptoms and major depression, but also with neurodegenerative and psychiatric comorbidities like Alzheimer’s disease, mild cognitive impairment, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder and panic disorder. Beyond epidemiological evidence, genomic studies identified consistent co-heritability based on common genetic variants between PDW and depression, as well as between PDW and Parkinson disease risk. Overall, this evidence suggests PDW as a very promising candidate biomarker for MDD and its comorbidities to investigate in the future.

Lastly, platelet serotonin might not only be important in platelet activation and subsequent involvement in platelet-related pathologies that are co-morbid with MDD, but also for its role as an epigenetic modulator in the serotonylation, a covalent posttranslational modification occurring at the level of histones thereby influencing gene expression [317]. Indeed, epigenetics has been hypothesized to play a major role in the etiology of depression [318–320]. In this view, serotonylation could represent a platelet-mediated link between serotonin and depression onset, a hypothesis which warrants further investigation.

As it appears from these open issues, much remains to be done to clarify the relationship between platelets, depression and its comorbidities in detail. This review tries to lay out at least some pieces of the puzzle for investigators in the field, having the ambition to expand into future research on this topic.

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Abbreviations

A β peptides	Amyloid β peptides
AD	Alzheimer's disease
ADD	Anxiety–depressive disorder
ADHD	Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder
ADP	Adenosine 5'-diphosphate
ALS	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
APP	Amyloid precursor protein
ASD	Autism spectrum disorder
ATP	Adenosine 5'-triphosphate
β TG	β -thromboglobulin
<i>BACE1</i>	β site APP cleaving enzyme 1
BDNF	Brain-derived neurotrophic factor
CAD	Coronary artery disease
CD40L	CD40 ligand
CHD	Coronary heart disease
CHF	Congestive heart failure
CVD	Cardiovascular disease
EAAT2	Glial glutamate transporter GLT-1
GABA	Gamma-aminobutyric acid
GAD	Generalized anxiety disorder
glm	Generalized linear model
GPIb	Glycoprotein Ib
GPVI	Glycoprotein VI
GWAS	Genome-wide association study
MAO-B	Monoamine oxidase B
MCI	Mild cognitive impairment
MDD	Major depressive disorder
MI	Myocardial infarction
MMSE	Mini-mental state examination
MPV	Mean platelet volume
MR	Mendelian randomization
PanDis	Panic disorder
PAR1	Protease-activated receptor 1
PCT	Plateletcrit
PD	Parkinson disease
PDW	Platelet distribution width
PF4	Platelet factor 4
PKC	Protein kinase C
P-LCR	Platelet-to-larger cell ratio
PLC γ 2	1-phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2
Plt	Platelet count
PTSD	Post-traumatic stress disorder
SERT	Serotonin transporter
SNP	Single nucleotide polymorphism
SSRIs	Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors
TDP-43	43 kDa TAR DNA-binding protein
TRAP-6	Thrombin receptor activating peptide 6
TxA2	Thromboxane A2
VMAT2	Vesicular monoamine transporter 2
5-HT	5-hydroxytryptamine
5-HT2A	Serotonin receptor 2A
5-HT3A	Serotonin receptor 3A

References

1. Adolfsson, R.; Gottfries, C.G.; Orelund, L.; Wiberg, A.; Winblad, B. Increased activity of brain and platelet monoamine oxidase in dementia of Alzheimer type. *Life Sci.* **1980**, *27*, 1029–1034. [[CrossRef](#)]
2. Anthony, M.; Hinterberger, H.; Lance, J.W. Studies of serotonin metabolism in migraine. *Proc. Aust. Assoc. Neurol.* **1968**, *5*, 109–112. [[PubMed](#)]
3. Boullin, D.J.; O'Brien, R.A. Accumulation of dopamine by blood platelets from normal subjects and parkinsonian patients under treatment with L-DOPA. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* **1970**, *39*, 779–788. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
4. Boullin, D.J.; Coleman, M.; O'Brien, R.A. Abnormalities in platelet 5-hydroxytryptamine efflux in patients with infantile autism. *Nature* **1970**, *226*, 371–372. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
5. Todrick, A.; Tait, A.C.; Marshall, E.F. Blood platelet 5-hydroxytryptamine levels in psychiatric patients. *J. Ment. Sci.* **1960**, *106*, 884–890. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Ritvo, E.R.; Yuwiler, A.; Geller, E.; Ornitz, E.M.; Saeger, K.; Plotkin, S. Increased blood serotonin and platelets in early infantile autism. *Arch. Gen. Psychiatry* **1970**, *23*, 566–572. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Goubau, C.; Buysse, G.M.; Di Michele, M.; Van Geet, C.; Freson, K. Regulated granule trafficking in platelets and neurons: A common molecular machinery. *Eur. J. Paediatr. Neurol.* **2013**, *17*, 117–125. [[CrossRef](#)]
8. Goubau, C.; Buysse, G.M.; Van Geet, C.; Freson, K. The contribution of platelet studies to the understanding of disease mechanisms in complex and monogenetic neurological disorders. *Dev. Med. Child. Neurol.* **2014**, *56*, 724–731. [[CrossRef](#)]
9. Padmakumar, M.; Van Raes, E.; Van Geet, C.; Freson, K. Blood platelet research in autism spectrum disorders: In search of biomarkers. *Res. Pract. Thromb. Haemost.* **2019**, *3*, 566–577. [[CrossRef](#)]
10. Canobbio, I.; Guidetti, G.F.; Torti, M. Platelets in neurological disorders. In *Platelets in Thrombotic and Non-Thrombotic Disorders*; Gresele, P.K.N., Lopez, J.A., Page, C.P., Eds.; Springer International: Cham, Switzerland, 2017; pp. 513–530.
11. Canobbio, I. Blood platelets: Circulating mirrors of neurons? *Res. Pract. Thromb. Haemost.* **2019**, *3*, 564–565. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Behari, M.; Shrivastava, M. Role of platelets in neurodegenerative diseases: A universal pathophysiology. *Int. J. Neurosci.* **2013**, *123*, 287–299. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
13. Ehrlich, D.; Humpel, C. Platelets in psychiatric disorders. *World J. Psychiatry* **2012**, *2*, 91–94. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
14. Pluta, R.; Ulamek-Kozioł, M.; Januszewski, S.; Czuczwar, S.J. Platelets, lymphocytes and erythrocytes from Alzheimer's disease patients: The quest for blood cell-based biomarkers. *Folia Neuropathol.* **2018**, *56*, 14–20. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
15. Asor, E.; Ben-Shachar, D. Platelets: A possible glance into brain biological processes in schizophrenia. *World J. Psychiatry* **2012**, *2*, 124–133. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
16. Pellerin, D.; Lortie, A.; Corbin, F. Platelets as a surrogate disease model of neurodevelopmental disorders: Insights from Fragile X Syndrome. *Platelets* **2018**, *29*, 113–124. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
17. Hasin, D.S.; Sarvet, A.L.; Meyers, J.L.; Saha, T.D.; Ruan, W.J.; Stohl, M.; Grant, B.F. Epidemiology of Adult DSM-5 Major Depressive Disorder and Its Specifiers in the United States. *JAMA Psychiatry* **2018**, *75*, 336–346. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
18. Maffioletti, E.; Minelli, A.; Tardito, D.; Gennarelli, M. Blues in the Brain and Beyond: Molecular Bases of Major Depressive Disorder and Relative Pharmacological and Non-Pharmacological Treatments. *Genes* **2020**, *11*, 1089. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Reed, G.L.; Fitzgerald, M.L.; Polgar, J. Molecular mechanisms of platelet exocytosis: Insights into the “secrete” life of thrombocytes. *Blood* **2000**, *96*, 3334–3342.
20. Ponomarev, E.D. Fresh Evidence for Platelets as Neuronal and Innate Immune Cells: Their Role in the Activation, Differentiation, and Deactivation of Th1, Th17, and Tregs during Tissue Inflammation. *Front. Immunol.* **2018**, *9*, 406. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Canobbio, I.; Guidetti, G.F.; Oliviero, B.; Manganaro, D.; Vara, D.; Torti, M.; Pula, G. Amyloid beta-peptide-dependent activation of human platelets: Essential role for Ca²⁺ and ADP in aggregation and thrombus formation. *Biochem. J.* **2014**, *462*, 513–523. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Yamamoto, H.; Gurney, M.E. Human platelets contain brain-derived neurotrophic factor. *J. Neurosci.* **1990**, *10*, 3469–3478. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

23. Tsai, S.J. Critical Issues in BDNF Val66Met Genetic Studies of Neuropsychiatric Disorders. *Front. Mol. Neurosci.* **2018**, *11*, 156. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
24. Fuchikami, M.; Morinobu, S.; Segawa, M.; Okamoto, Y.; Yamawaki, S.; Ozaki, N.; Inoue, T.; Kusumi, I.; Koyama, T.; Tsuchiyama, K.; et al. DNA methylation profiles of the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) gene as a potent diagnostic biomarker in major depression. *PLoS ONE* **2011**, *6*, e23881. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
25. Bozzini, S.; Gambelli, P.; Boiocchi, C.; Schirinzi, S.; Falcone, R.; Buzzi, P.; Storti, C.; Falcone, C. Coronary artery disease and depression: Possible role of brain-derived neurotrophic factor and serotonin transporter gene polymorphisms. *Int. J. Mol. Med.* **2009**, *24*, 813–818. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
26. Kim, J.M.; Stewart, R.; Kim, J.W.; Kang, H.J.; Lee, J.Y.; Kim, S.Y.; Kim, S.W.; Shin, I.S.; Hong, Y.J.; Ahn, Y.; et al. Modifying effects of depression on the association between BDNF methylation and prognosis of acute coronary syndrome. *Brain Behav. Immun.* **2019**, *81*, 422–429. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Amadio, P.; Colombo, G.I.; Tarantino, E.; Gianellini, S.; Ieraci, A.; Briosci, M.; Banfi, C.; Werba, J.P.; Parolari, A.; Lee, F.S.; et al. BDNFVal66met polymorphism: A potential bridge between depression and thrombosis. *Eur. Heart J.* **2017**, *38*, 1426–1435. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Bondy, B. Common genetic factors for depression and cardiovascular disease. *Dialogues Clin. Neurosci.* **2007**, *9*, 19–28.
29. Liu, Y.Q.; Su, G.B.; Duan, C.H.; Wang, J.H.; Liu, H.M.; Feng, N.; Wang, Q.X.; Liu, X.E.; Zhang, J. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor gene polymorphisms are associated with coronary artery disease-related depression and antidepressant response. *Mol. Med. Rep.* **2014**, *10*, 3247–3253. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Negri, L. Vittorio Ersamer (1909–1999). *Med. Secoli* **2006**, *18*, 97–113.
31. Janusonis, S. Serotonin dynamics in and around the central nervous system: Is autism solvable without fundamental insights? *Int. J. Dev. Neurosci.* **2014**, *39*, 9–15. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Jackman, H.; Luchins, D.; Meltzer, H.Y. Platelet serotonin levels in schizophrenia: Relationship to race and psychopathology. *Biol. Psychiatry* **1983**, *18*, 887–902. [[PubMed](#)]
33. Owens, M.J.; Nemeroff, C.B. Role of serotonin in the pathophysiology of depression: Focus on the serotonin transporter. *Clin. Chem.* **1994**, *40*, 288–295. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
34. Pletscher, A.; Laubscher, A. Blood platelets as models for neurons: Uses and limitations. *J. Neural. Transm. Suppl.* **1980**. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Pletscher, A.; Laubscher, A.; Graf, M.; Saner, A. Blood platelets as models for central 5-hydroxytryptaminergic neurons. *Ann. Biol. Clin. (Paris)* **1979**, *37*, 35–39.
36. De Gaetano, G. Blood platelets as a pharmacological model of serotonergic synaptosomes. In *Platelets: A Multidisciplinary Approach*; de Gaetano, G., Garattini, S., Eds.; Raven Press: New York, NY, USA, 1978; pp. 373–384.
37. Buczko, W.; De Gaetano, G.; Garattini, S. Influence of some tricyclic antidepressive drugs on the uptake of 5-hydroxytryptamine by rat blood platelets. *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.* **1974**, *26*, 814–815. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Buczko, W.; De Gaetano, G.; Garattini, S. Effect of fenfluramine on 5-hydroxytryptamine uptake and release by rat blood platelets. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* **1975**, *53*, 563–568. [[CrossRef](#)]
39. Buczko, W.; De Gaetano, G.; Garattini, S. Effect of some anorectic agents on the uptake and release of 5-hydroxytryptamine by blood platelets of rats. *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.* **1975**, *27*, 366–368. [[CrossRef](#)]
40. Wielosz, M.; Dall'olio, A.; de Gaetano, G.; Garattini, S. Effect of two non tricyclic antidepressant drugs on [¹⁴C]5-hydroxytryptamine uptake by rat platelets. *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.* **1977**, *29*, 546–549. [[CrossRef](#)]
41. Lampugnani, M.G.; Buczko, W.; Ceci, A.; Mennini, A.; de Gaetano, G. Normal serotonin uptake by blood platelets and brain synaptosomes but selective impairment of platelet serotonin storage in mice with Chediack-Higashi syndrome. *Life Sci.* **1986**, *38*, 2193–2198. [[CrossRef](#)]
42. Hergovich, N.; Aigner, M.; Eichler, H.G.; Entlicher, J.; Drucker, C.; Jilma, B. Paroxetine decreases platelet serotonin storage and platelet function in human beings. *Clin. Pharmacol. Ther.* **2000**, *68*, 435–442. [[CrossRef](#)]
43. Castermans, D.; Volders, K.; Crepel, A.; Backx, L.; De Vos, R.; Freson, K.; Meulemans, S.; Vermeesch, J.R.; Schrandt-Stumpel, C.T.; De Rijk, P.; et al. SCAMP5, NBEA and AMISYN: Three candidate genes for autism involved in secretion of large dense-core vesicles. *Hum. Mol. Genet.* **2010**, *19*, 1368–1378. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
44. Tyce, G.M. Origin and metabolism of serotonin. *J. Cardiovasc. Pharmacol.* **1990**, *16* (Suppl. 3), S1–S7. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
45. Jonnakuty, C.; Gragnoli, C. What do we know about serotonin? *J. Cell Physiol.* **2008**, *217*, 301–306. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

46. Lesch, K.P.; Wolozin, B.L.; Murphy, D.L.; Reiderer, P. Primary structure of the human platelet serotonin uptake site: Identity with the brain serotonin transporter. *J. Neurochem.* **1993**, *60*, 2319–2322. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
47. Holinstat, M. Normal platelet function. *Cancer Metastasis Rev.* **2017**, *36*, 195–198. [[CrossRef](#)]
48. Brenner, B.; Harney, J.T.; Ahmed, B.A.; Jeffus, B.C.; Unal, R.; Mehta, J.L.; Kilic, F. Plasma serotonin levels and the platelet serotonin transporter. *J. Neurochem.* **2007**, *102*, 206–215. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
49. McNicol, A.; Israels, S.J. Platelet dense granules: Structure, function and implications for haemostasis. *Thromb. Res.* **1999**, *95*, 1–18. [[CrossRef](#)]
50. Mercado, C.P.; Kilic, F. Molecular mechanisms of SERT in platelets: Regulation of plasma serotonin levels. *Mol. Interv.* **2010**, *10*, 231–241. [[CrossRef](#)]
51. Holtje, M.; Winter, S.; Walther, D.; Pahner, I.; Hortnagl, H.; Ottersen, O.P.; Bader, M.; Ahnert-Hilger, G. The vesicular monoamine content regulates VMAT2 activity through Galphaq in mouse platelets. Evidence for autoregulation of vesicular transmitter uptake. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2003**, *278*, 15850–15858. [[CrossRef](#)]
52. Mammadova-Bach, E.; Mauler, M.; Braun, A.; Duerschmied, D. Autocrine and paracrine regulatory functions of platelet serotonin. *Platelets* **2018**, *29*, 541–548. [[CrossRef](#)]
53. Cerrito, F.; Lazzaro, M.P.; Gaudio, E.; Arminio, P.; Aloisi, G. 5HT2-receptors and serotonin release: Their role in human platelet aggregation. *Life Sci.* **1993**, *53*, 209–215. [[CrossRef](#)]
54. Brunk, I.; Blex, C.; Rachakonda, S.; Holtje, M.; Winter, S.; Pahner, I.; Walther, D.J.; Ahnert-Hilger, G. The first luminal domain of vesicular monoamine transporters mediates G-protein-dependent regulation of transmitter uptake. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2006**, *281*, 33373–33385. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
55. Li, N.; Wallen, N.H.; Ladjevardi, M.; Hjemdahl, P. Effects of serotonin on platelet activation in whole blood. *Blood Coagul. Fibrinolysis* **1997**, *8*, 517–523. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
56. Ostrowitzki, S.; Rao, M.L.; Redei, J.; Andres, A.H. Concurrence of cortex and platelet serotonin2 receptor binding characteristics in the individual and the putative regulation by serotonin. *J. Neural Transm. Gen. Sect.* **1993**, *93*, 27–35. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
57. Andres, A.H.; Rao, M.L.; Ostrowitzki, S.; Entzian, W. Human brain cortex and platelet serotonin2 receptor binding properties and their regulation by endogenous serotonin. *Life Sci.* **1993**, *52*, 313–321. [[CrossRef](#)]
58. Cook, E.H., Jr.; Fletcher, K.E.; Wainwright, M.; Marks, N.; Yan, S.Y.; Leventhal, B.L. Primary structure of the human platelet serotonin 5-HT2A receptor: Identify with frontal cortex serotonin 5-HT2A receptor. *J. Neurochem.* **1994**, *63*, 465–469. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
59. Owens, M.J.; Nemeroff, C.B. The serotonin transporter and depression. *Depress. Anxiety* **1998**, *8* (Suppl. 1), 5–12. [[CrossRef](#)]
60. Schins, A.; Honig, A.; Crijns, H.; Baur, L.; Hamulyak, K. Increased coronary events in depressed cardiovascular patients: 5-HT2A receptor as missing link? *Psychosom. Med.* **2003**, *65*, 729–737. [[CrossRef](#)]
61. Hrdina, P.D.; Bakish, D.; Chudzik, J.; Ravindran, A.; Lapierre, Y.D. Serotonergic markers in platelets of patients with major depression: Upregulation of 5-HT2 receptors. *J. Psychiatry Neurosci.* **1995**, *20*, 11–19.
62. McBride, P.A.; Mann, J.J.; Polley, M.J.; Wiley, A.J.; Sweeney, J.A. Assessment of binding indices and physiological responsiveness of the 5-HT2 receptor on human platelets. *Life Sci.* **1987**, *40*, 1799–1809. [[CrossRef](#)]
63. Pandey, G.N.; Pandey, S.C.; Janicak, P.G.; Marks, R.C.; Davis, J.M. Platelet serotonin-2 receptor binding sites in depression and suicide. *Biol. Psychiatry* **1990**, *28*, 215–222. [[CrossRef](#)]
64. Leake, A.; Fairbairn, A.F.; McKeith, I.G.; Ferrier, I.N. Studies on the serotonin uptake binding site in major depressive disorder and control post-mortem brain: Neurochemical and clinical correlates. *Psychiatry Res.* **1991**, *39*, 155–165. [[CrossRef](#)]
65. Malison, R.T.; Price, L.H.; Berman, R.; van Dyck, C.H.; Pelton, G.H.; Carpenter, L.; Sanacora, G.; Owens, M.J.; Nemeroff, C.B.; Rajeevan, N.; et al. Reduced brain serotonin transporter availability in major depression as measured by [¹²³I]-2 beta-carbomethoxy-3 beta-(4-iodophenyl)tropane and single photon emission computed tomography. *Biol. Psychiatry* **1998**, *44*, 1090–1098. [[CrossRef](#)]
66. Stain-Malmgren, R.; Khoury, A.E.; Aberg-Wistedt, A.; Tham, A. Serotonergic function in major depression and effect of sertraline and paroxetine treatment. *Int. Clin. Psychopharmacol.* **2001**, *16*, 93–101. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
67. Willeit, M.; Sitte, H.H.; Thierry, N.; Michalek, K.; Praschak-Rieder, N.; Zill, P.; Winkler, D.; Brannath, W.; Fischer, M.B.; Bondy, B.; et al. Enhanced serotonin transporter function during depression in seasonal affective disorder. *Neuropsychopharmacology* **2008**, *33*, 1503–1513. [[CrossRef](#)]
68. Davi, G.; Patrono, C. Platelet activation and atherothrombosis. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2007**, *357*, 2482–2494. [[CrossRef](#)]
69. Berger, M.; Gray, J.A.; Roth, B.L. The expanded biology of serotonin. *Annu. Rev. Med.* **2009**, *60*, 355–366. [[CrossRef](#)]

70. Ahern, G.P. 5-HT and the immune system. *Curr. Opin. Pharmacol.* **2011**, *11*, 29–33. [[CrossRef](#)]
71. Pelletier, M.; Siegel, R.M. Wishing away inflammation? New links between serotonin and TNF signaling. *Mol. Interv.* **2009**, *9*, 299–301. [[CrossRef](#)]
72. Schoenichen, C.; Bode, C.; Duerschmied, D. Role of platelet serotonin in innate immune cell recruitment. *Front. Biosci. (Landmark Ed.)* **2019**, *24*, 514–526.
73. Quintero-Villegas, A.; Valdes-Ferrer, S.I. Role of 5-HT7 receptors in the immune system in health and disease. *Mol. Med.* **2019**, *26*, 2. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
74. Ziu, E.; Hadden, C.; Li, Y.; Lowery, C.L., 3rd; Singh, P.; Ucer, S.S.; Mercado, C.P.; Gu, H.H.; Kilic, F. Effect of serotonin on platelet function in cocaine exposed blood. *Sci. Rep.* **2014**, *4*, 5945. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
75. Duerschmied, D.; Suidan, G.L.; Demers, M.; Herr, N.; Carbo, C.; Brill, A.; Cifuni, S.M.; Mauler, M.; Cicko, S.; Bader, M.; et al. Platelet serotonin promotes the recruitment of neutrophils to sites of acute inflammation in mice. *Blood* **2013**, *121*, 1008–1015. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
76. Nakamura, K.; Kariyazono, H.; Moriyama, Y.; Toyohira, H.; Kubo, H.; Yotsumoto, G.; Taira, A.; Yamada, K. Effects of sarpogrelate hydrochloride on platelet aggregation, and its relation to the release of serotonin and P-selectin. *Blood Coagul. Fibrinolysis* **1999**, *10*, 513–519. [[CrossRef](#)]
77. Subramaniam, M.; Saffaripour, S.; Van De Water, L.; Frenette, P.S.; Mayadas, T.N.; Hynes, R.O.; Wagner, D.D. Role of endothelial selectins in wound repair. *Am. J. Pathol.* **1997**, *150*, 1701–1709.
78. Palmer, D.S.; Aye, M.T.; Ganz, P.R.; Halpenny, M.; Hashemi, S. Adenosine nucleotides and serotonin stimulate von Willebrand factor release from cultured human endothelial cells. *Thromb. Haemost.* **1994**, *72*, 132–139.
79. Park, H.; Poo, M.M. Neurotrophin regulation of neural circuit development and function. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* **2013**, *14*, 7–23. [[CrossRef](#)]
80. Zagrebelsky, M.; Korte, M. Form follows function: BDNF and its involvement in sculpting the function and structure of synapses. *Neuropharmacology* **2014**, *76 Pt C*, 628–638. [[CrossRef](#)]
81. Huang, E.J.; Reichardt, L.F. Neurotrophins: Roles in neuronal development and function. *Annu. Rev. Neurosci.* **2001**, *24*, 677–736. [[CrossRef](#)]
82. Lindsay, R.M.; Wiegand, S.J.; Altar, C.A.; DiStefano, P.S. Neurotrophic factors: From molecule to man. *Trends Neurosci.* **1994**, *17*, 182–190. [[CrossRef](#)]
83. Bus, B.A.; Molendijk, M.L.; Penninx, B.J.; Buitelaar, J.K.; Kenis, G.; Prickaerts, J.; Elzinga, B.M.; Voshaar, R.C. Determinants of serum brain-derived neurotrophic factor. *Psychoneuroendocrinology* **2011**, *36*, 228–239. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
84. Karege, F.; Bondolfi, G.; Gervasoni, N.; Schwald, M.; Aubry, J.M.; Bertschy, G. Low brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) levels in serum of depressed patients probably results from lowered platelet BDNF release unrelated to platelet reactivity. *Biol. Psychiatry* **2005**, *57*, 1068–1072. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
85. Fujimura, H.; Altar, C.A.; Chen, R.; Nakamura, T.; Nakahashi, T.; Kambayashi, J.; Sun, B.; Tandon, N.N. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor is stored in human platelets and released by agonist stimulation. *Thromb. Haemost.* **2002**, *87*, 728–734. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
86. Begliuomini, S.; Casarosa, E.; Pluchino, N.; Lenzi, E.; Centofanti, M.; Freschi, L.; Pieri, M.; Genazzani, A.D.; Luisi, S.; Genazzani, A.R. Influence of endogenous and exogenous sex hormones on plasma brain-derived neurotrophic factor. *Hum. Reprod.* **2007**, *22*, 995–1002. [[CrossRef](#)]
87. Saito, S.; Watanabe, K.; Hashimoto, E.; Saito, T. Low serum BDNF and food intake regulation: A possible new explanation of the pathophysiology of eating disorders. *Prog. Neuropsychopharmacol. Biol. Psychiatry* **2009**, *33*, 312–316. [[CrossRef](#)]
88. Chacon-Fernandez, P.; Sauberli, K.; Colzani, M.; Moreau, T.; Ghevaert, C.; Barde, Y.A. Brain-derived Neurotrophic Factor in Megakaryocytes. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2016**, *291*, 9872–9881. [[CrossRef](#)]
89. Lommatzsch, M.; Zingler, D.; Schuhbaeck, K.; Schloetcke, K.; Zingler, C.; Schuff-Werner, P.; Virchow, J.C. The impact of age, weight and gender on BDNF levels in human platelets and plasma. *Neurobiol. Aging* **2005**, *26*, 115–123. [[CrossRef](#)]
90. Radka, S.F.; Holst, P.A.; Fritsche, M.; Altar, C.A. Presence of brain-derived neurotrophic factor in brain and human and rat but not mouse serum detected by a sensitive and specific immunoassay. *Brain Res.* **1996**, *709*, 122–301. [[CrossRef](#)]
91. Amadio, P.; Porro, B.; Sandrini, L.; Fiorelli, S.; Bonomi, A.; Cavalca, V.; Brambilla, M.; Camera, M.; Veglia, F.; Tremoli, E.; et al. Patho-physiological role of BDNF in fibrin clotting. *Sci. Rep.* **2019**, *9*, 389. [[CrossRef](#)]

92. Tamura, S.; Suzuki, H.; Hirowatari, Y.; Hatase, M.; Nagasawa, A.; Matsuno, K.; Kobayashi, S.; Moriyama, T. Release reaction of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) through PAR1 activation and its two distinct pools in human platelets. *Thromb. Res.* **2011**, *128*, e55–e61. [[CrossRef](#)]
93. Shimizu, E.; Hashimoto, K.; Watanabe, H.; Komatsu, N.; Okamura, N.; Koike, K.; Shinoda, N.; Nakazato, M.; Kumakiri, C.; Okada, S.; et al. Serum brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) levels in schizophrenia are indistinguishable from controls. *Neurosci. Lett.* **2003**, *351*, 111–114. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
94. Serra-Millas, M.; Lopez-Vilchez, I.; Navarro, V.; Galan, A.M.; Escolar, G.; Penades, R.; Catalan, R.; Fananas, L.; Arias, B.; Gasto, C. Changes in plasma and platelet BDNF levels induced by S-citalopram in major depression. *Psychopharmacology (Berl.)* **2011**, *216*, 1–8. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
95. Toyooka, K.; Asama, K.; Watanabe, Y.; Muratake, T.; Takahashi, M.; Someya, T.; Nawa, H. Decreased levels of brain-derived neurotrophic factor in serum of chronic schizophrenic patients. *Psychiatry Res.* **2002**, *110*, 249–257. [[CrossRef](#)]
96. Laske, C.; Stransky, E.; Leyhe, T.; Eschweiler, G.W.; Maetzler, W.; Wittorf, A.; Soekadar, S.; Richartz, E.; Koehler, N.; Bartels, M.; et al. BDNF serum and CSF concentrations in Alzheimer's disease, normal pressure hydrocephalus and healthy controls. *J. Psychiatr. Res.* **2007**, *41*, 387–394. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
97. Monteleone, P.; Fabrazzo, M.; Martiadis, V.; Serritella, C.; Pannuto, M.; Maj, M. Circulating brain-derived neurotrophic factor is decreased in women with anorexia and bulimia nervosa but not in women with binge-eating disorder: Relationships to co-morbid depression, psychopathology and hormonal variables. *Psychol. Med.* **2005**, *35*, 897–905. [[CrossRef](#)]
98. Duman, R.S.; Monteggia, L.M. A neurotrophic model for stress-related mood disorders. *Biol. Psychiatry* **2006**, *59*, 1116–1127. [[CrossRef](#)]
99. Liu, C.Y.; Jiang, X.X.; Zhu, Y.H.; Wei, D.N. Metabotropic glutamate receptor 5 antagonist 2-methyl-6-(phenylethynyl)pyridine produces antidepressant effects in rats: Role of brain-derived neurotrophic factor. *Neuroscience* **2012**, *223*, 219–224. [[CrossRef](#)]
100. Santana, J.; Marzolo, M.P. The functions of Reelin in membrane trafficking and cytoskeletal dynamics: Implications for neuronal migration, polarization and differentiation. *Biochem. J.* **2017**, *474*, 3137–3165. [[CrossRef](#)]
101. Jossin, Y. Reelin Functions, Mechanisms of Action and Signaling Pathways During Brain Development and Maturation. *Biomolecules* **2020**, *10*, 964. [[CrossRef](#)]
102. Tissir, F.; Goffinet, A.M. Reelin and brain development. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* **2003**, *4*, 496–505. [[CrossRef](#)]
103. Smalheiser, N.R.; Costa, E.; Guidotti, A.; Impagnatiello, F.; Auta, J.; Lacor, P.; Kriho, V.; Pappas, G.D. Expression of reelin in adult mammalian blood, liver, pituitary pars intermedia, and adrenal chromaffin cells. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **2000**, *97*, 1281–1286. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
104. Ding, Y.; Huang, L.; Xian, X.; Yuhanna, I.S.; Wasser, C.R.; Frotscher, M.; Mineo, C.; Shaul, P.W.; Herz, J. Loss of Reelin protects against atherosclerosis by reducing leukocyte-endothelial cell adhesion and lesion macrophage accumulation. *Sci. Signal.* **2016**, *9*, ra29. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
105. Tseng, W.L.; Chen, T.H.; Huang, C.C.; Huang, Y.H.; Yeh, C.F.; Tsai, H.J.; Lee, H.Y.; Kao, C.Y.; Lin, S.W.; Liao, H.R.; et al. Impaired thrombin generation in Reelin-deficient mice: A potential role of plasma Reelin in hemostasis. *J. Thromb. Haemost.* **2014**, *12*, 2054–2064. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
106. Gowert, N.S.; Kruger, I.; Klier, M.; Donner, L.; Kipkeew, F.; Gliem, M.; Bradshaw, N.J.; Lutz, D.; Kober, S.; Langer, H.; et al. Loss of Reelin protects mice against arterial thrombosis by impairing integrin activation and thrombus formation under high shear conditions. *Cell Signal.* **2017**, *40*, 210–221. [[CrossRef](#)]
107. Krueger, I.; Gremer, L.; Mangels, L.; Klier, M.; Jurk, K.; Willbold, D.; Bock, H.H.; Elvers, M. Reelin Amplifies GPVI Activation and AlphaIIb Beta3 Integrin Outside-In Signaling via PLC Gamma 2 and Rho GTPases. *Arterioscler. Thromb. Vasc. Biol.* **2020**, ATVBAHA120314902. [[CrossRef](#)]
108. Tseng, W.L.; Huang, C.L.; Chong, K.Y.; Liao, C.H.; Stern, A.; Cheng, J.C.; Tseng, C.P. Reelin is a platelet protein and functions as a positive regulator of platelet spreading on fibrinogen. *Cell Mol. Life Sci.* **2010**, *67*, 641–653. [[CrossRef](#)]
109. Panza, F.; Lozupone, M.; Logroscino, G.; Imbimbo, B.P. A critical appraisal of amyloid-beta-targeting therapies for Alzheimer disease. *Nat. Rev. Neurol.* **2019**, *15*, 73–88. [[CrossRef](#)]
110. Sierksma, A.S.; van den Hove, D.L.; Steinbusch, H.W.; Prickaerts, J. Major depression, cognitive dysfunction and Alzheimer's disease: Is there a link? *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* **2010**, *626*, 72–82. [[CrossRef](#)]

111. Donovan, N.J.; Locascio, J.J.; Marshall, G.A.; Gatchel, J.; Hanseeuw, B.J.; Rentz, D.M.; Johnson, K.A.; Sperling, R.A.; Harvard Aging Brain, S. Longitudinal Association of Amyloid Beta and Anxious-Depressive Symptoms in Cognitively Normal Older Adults. *Am. J. Psychiatry* **2018**, *175*, 530–537. [[CrossRef](#)]
112. Chung, J.K.; Plitman, E.; Nakajima, S.; Chow, T.W.; Chakravarty, M.M.; Caravaggio, F.; Gerretsen, P.; Brown, E.E.; Iwata, Y.; Mulsant, B.H.; et al. Lifetime History of Depression Predicts Increased Amyloid-beta Accumulation in Patients with Mild Cognitive Impairment. *J. Alzheimers Dis.* **2015**, *45*, 907–919. [[CrossRef](#)]
113. Kitazume, S.; Yoshihisa, A.; Yamaki, T.; Oikawa, M.; Tachida, Y.; Ogawa, K.; Imamaki, R.; Hagiwara, Y.; Kinoshita, N.; Takeishi, Y.; et al. Soluble amyloid precursor protein 770 is released from inflamed endothelial cells and activated platelets: A novel biomarker for acute coronary syndrome. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2012**, *287*, 40817–40825. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
114. Melchor, J.P.; Van Nostrand, W.E. Fibrillar amyloid beta-protein mediates the pathologic accumulation of its secreted precursor in human cerebrovascular smooth muscle cells. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2000**, *275*, 9782–9791. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
115. De Meyer, G.R.; De Cleen, D.M.; Cooper, S.; Knaapen, M.W.; Jans, D.M.; Martinet, W.; Herman, A.G.; Bult, H.; Kockx, M.M. Platelet phagocytosis and processing of beta-amyloid precursor protein as a mechanism of macrophage activation in atherosclerosis. *Circ. Res.* **2002**, *90*, 1197–1204. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
116. Stakos, D.A.; Stamatiopoulos, K.; Bampatsias, D.; Sachse, M.; Zormpas, E.; Vlachogiannis, N.I.; Tual-Chalot, S.; Stellos, K. The Alzheimer's Disease Amyloid-Beta Hypothesis in Cardiovascular Aging and Disease: JACC Focus Seminar. *J. Am. Coll. Cardiol.* **2020**, *75*, 952–967. [[CrossRef](#)]
117. Chong, Y.H.; Sung, J.H.; Shin, S.A.; Chung, J.H.; Suh, Y.H. Effects of the beta-amyloid and carboxyl-terminal fragment of Alzheimer's amyloid precursor protein on the production of the tumor necrosis factor-alpha and matrix metalloproteinase-9 by human monocytic THP-1. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2001**, *276*, 23511–23517. [[CrossRef](#)]
118. Vassar, R.; Bennett, B.D.; Babu-Khan, S.; Kahn, S.; Mendiaz, E.A.; Denis, P.; Teplow, D.B.; Ross, S.; Amarante, P.; Loeloff, R.; et al. Beta-secretase cleavage of Alzheimer's amyloid precursor protein by the transmembrane aspartic protease BACE. *Science* **1999**, *286*, 735–741. [[CrossRef](#)]
119. Tanzi, R.E.; Bertram, L. Twenty years of the Alzheimer's disease amyloid hypothesis: A genetic perspective. *Cell* **2005**, *120*, 545–555. [[CrossRef](#)]
120. Kang, J.; Lemaire, H.G.; Unterbeck, A.; Salbaum, J.M.; Masters, C.L.; Grzeschik, K.H.; Multhaup, G.; Beyreuther, K.; Muller-Hill, B. The precursor of Alzheimer's disease amyloid A4 protein resembles a cell-surface receptor. *Nature* **1987**, *325*, 733–736. [[CrossRef](#)]
121. Miura, S.; Yoshihisa, A.; Misaka, T.; Yamaki, T.; Kojima, T.; Toyokawa, M.; Ogawa, K.; Shimura, H.; Yamamoto, N.; Kasahara, K.; et al. Amyloid precursor protein 770 is specifically expressed and released from platelets. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2020**, *295*, 13194–13201. [[CrossRef](#)]
122. Van Nostrand, W.E.; Schmaier, A.H.; Farrow, J.S.; Cunningham, D.D. Protease nexin-II (amyloid beta-protein precursor): A platelet alpha-granule protein. *Science* **1990**, *248*, 745–748. [[CrossRef](#)]
123. Canobbio, I.; Visconte, C.; Momi, S.; Guidetti, G.F.; Zara, M.; Canino, J.; Falcinelli, E.; Gresele, P.; Torti, M. Platelet amyloid precursor protein is a modulator of venous thromboembolism in mice. *Blood* **2017**, *130*, 527–536. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
124. Jarre, A.; Gowert, N.S.; Donner, L.; Munzer, P.; Klier, M.; Borst, O.; Schaller, M.; Lang, F.; Korth, C.; Elvers, M. Pre-activated blood platelets and a pro-thrombotic phenotype in APP23 mice modeling Alzheimer's disease. *Cell Signal.* **2014**, *26*, 2040–2050. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
125. Visconte, C.; Canino, J.; Guidetti, G.F.; Zara, M.; Seppi, C.; Abubaker, A.A.; Pula, G.; Torti, M.; Canobbio, I. Amyloid precursor protein is required for in vitro platelet adhesion to amyloid peptides and potentiation of thrombus formation. *Cell Signal.* **2018**, *52*, 95–102. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
126. Mazinani, N.; Strilchuk, A.W.; Baylis, J.R.; Hur, W.S.; Jefferies, W.A.; Kastrup, C.J. Bleeding is increased in amyloid precursor protein knockout mouse. *Res. Pract. Thromb. Haemost.* **2020**, *4*, 823–828. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
127. Herczenik, E.; Bouma, B.; Korpelaar, S.J.; Strangi, R.; Zeng, Q.; Gros, P.; Van Eck, M.; Van Berkel, T.J.; Gebbink, M.F.; Akkerman, J.W. Activation of human platelets by misfolded proteins. *Arterioscler. Thromb. Vasc. Biol.* **2007**, *27*, 1657–1665. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
128. Donner, L.; Falker, K.; Gremer, L.; Klinker, S.; Pagani, G.; Ljungberg, L.U.; Lothmann, K.; Rizzi, F.; Schaller, M.; Gohlke, H.; et al. Platelets contribute to amyloid-beta aggregation in cerebral vessels through integrin alphaIIb beta3-induced outside-in signaling and clusterin release. *Sci. Signal.* **2016**, *9*, ra52. [[CrossRef](#)]

129. Shen, M.Y.; Hsiao, G.; Fong, T.H.; Chen, H.M.; Chou, D.S.; Lin, C.H.; Sheu, J.R.; Hsu, C.Y. Amyloid beta peptide-activated signal pathways in human platelets. *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* **2008**, *588*, 259–266. [[CrossRef](#)]
130. Walsh, T.G.; Berndt, M.C.; Carrim, N.; Cowman, J.; Kenny, D.; Metharom, P. The role of Nox1 and Nox2 in GPVI-dependent platelet activation and thrombus formation. *Redox Biol.* **2014**, *2*, 178–186. [[CrossRef](#)]
131. Abubaker, A.A.; Vara, D.; Visconte, C.; Eggleston, I.; Torti, M.; Canobbio, I.; Pula, G. Amyloid Peptide beta1-42 Induces Integrin alphaIIb beta3 Activation, Platelet Adhesion, and Thrombus Formation in a NADPH Oxidase-Dependent Manner. *Oxid. Med. Cell Longev.* **2019**, *2019*, 1050476. [[CrossRef](#)]
132. Cortes-Canteli, M.; Zamolodchikov, D.; Ahn, H.J.; Strickland, S.; Norris, E.H. Fibrinogen and altered hemostasis in Alzheimer's disease. *J. Alzheimers Dis.* **2012**, *32*, 599–608. [[CrossRef](#)]
133. Maciotta, S.; Meregalli, M.; Torrente, Y. The involvement of microRNAs in neurodegenerative diseases. *Front. Cell Neurosci.* **2013**, *7*, 265. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
134. Thomas, T.; Nadackal, T.G.; Thomas, K. Aspirin and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs inhibit amyloid-beta aggregation. *Neuroreport* **2001**, *12*, 3263–3267. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
135. Skovronsky, D.M.; Lee, V.M.; Pratico, D. Amyloid precursor protein and amyloid beta peptide in human platelets. Role of cyclooxygenase and protein kinase C. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2001**, *276*, 17036–17043. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
136. Chandra, S.; Jana, M.; Pahan, K. Aspirin Induces Lysosomal Biogenesis and Attenuates Amyloid Plaque Pathology in a Mouse Model of Alzheimer's Disease via PPARalpha. *J. Neurosci.* **2018**, *38*, 6682–6699. [[CrossRef](#)]
137. Musselman, D.L.; Tomer, A.; Manatunga, A.K.; Knight, B.T.; Porter, M.R.; Kasey, S.; Marzec, U.; Harker, L.A.; Nemeroff, C.B. Exaggerated platelet reactivity in major depression. *Am. J. Psychiatry* **1996**, *153*, 1313–1317. [[CrossRef](#)]
138. Pinto, V.L.; de Souza, P.F.; Brunini, T.M.; Oliveira, M.B.; Moss, M.B.; Siqueira, M.A.; Ferraz, M.R.; Mendes-Ribeiro, A.C. Low plasma levels of L-arginine, impaired intraplatelet nitric oxide and platelet hyperaggregability: Implications for cardiovascular disease in depressive patients. *J. Affect. Disord.* **2012**, *140*, 187–192. [[CrossRef](#)]
139. Morel-Kopp, M.C.; McLean, L.; Chen, Q.; Tofler, G.H.; Tennant, C.; Maddison, V.; Ward, C.M. The association of depression with platelet activation: Evidence for a treatment effect. *J. Thromb. Haemost.* **2009**, *7*, 573–581. [[CrossRef](#)]
140. Markovitz, J.H.; Shuster, J.L.; Chitwood, W.S.; May, R.S.; Tolbert, L.C. Platelet activation in depression and effects of sertraline treatment: An open-label study. *Am. J. Psychiatry* **2000**, *157*, 1006–1008. [[CrossRef](#)]
141. Ormonde do Carmo, M.B.; Mendes-Ribeiro, A.C.; Matsuura, C.; Pinto, V.L.; Mury, W.V.; Pinto, N.O.; Moss, M.B.; Ferraz, M.R.; Brunini, T.M. Major depression induces oxidative stress and platelet hyperaggregability. *J. Psychiatr. Res.* **2015**, *61*, 19–24. [[CrossRef](#)]
142. Hufner, K.; Kandler, C.; Koudouovoh-Tripp, P.; Egeter, J.; Hochstrasser, T.; Stemer, B.; Malik, P.; Giesinger, J.; Humpel, C.; Sperner-Unterweger, B. Bioprofiling of platelets in medicated patients with depression. *J. Affect. Disord.* **2015**, *172*, 81–88. [[CrossRef](#)]
143. Koudouovoh-Tripp, P.; Hufner, K.; Egeter, J.; Kandler, C.; Giesinger, J.M.; Sopper, S.; Humpel, C.; Sperner-Unterweger, B. Stress Enhances Proinflammatory Platelet Activity: The Impact of Acute and Chronic Mental Stress. *J. Neuroimmune Pharmacol.* **2020**. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
144. Canan, F.; Dikici, S.; Kutlucan, A.; Celbek, G.; Coskun, H.; Gungor, A.; Aydin, Y.; Kocaman, G. Association of mean platelet volume with DSM-IV major depression in a large community-based population: The MELEN study. *J. Psychiatr. Res.* **2012**, *46*, 298–302. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
145. Cai, L.; Xu, L.; Wei, L.; Chen, W. Relationship of Mean Platelet Volume To MDD: A Retrospective Study. *Shanghai Arch. Psychiatry* **2017**, *29*, 21–29. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
146. Bondade, S.; Supriya Seema, H.S.; Shivakumar, B.K. Mean Platelet Volume in Depression and Anxiety Disorder- a Hospital Based Case-control Study. *Int. Neuropsychiatr. Dis. J.* **2018**, *11*, 1–8. [[CrossRef](#)]
147. Ataoglu, A.; Canan, F. Mean platelet volume in patients with major depression: Effect of escitalopram treatment. *J. Clin. Psychopharmacol.* **2009**, *29*, 368–371. [[CrossRef](#)]
148. Aleksovski, B.; Neceva, V.; Vujovic, V.; Manusheva, N.; Rendevski, V.; Novotni, A.; Filipce, A.; Spasovska, A.; Sofijanovska, A.; Aleksovski, V.; et al. SSRI-reduced platelet reactivity in non-responding patients with life-long Recurrent Depressive Disorder: Detection and involved mechanisms. *Thromb. Res.* **2018**, *165*, 24–32. [[CrossRef](#)]

149. Gialluisi, A.; Izzi, B.; Di Castelnuovo, A.; Cerletti, C.; Donati, M.B.; de Gaetano, G.; Iacoviello, L. Revisiting the link between platelets and depression through genetic epidemiology: New insights from platelet distribution width. *Haematologica* **2019**. [[CrossRef](#)]
150. Gialluisi, A.; Bonaccio, M.; Di Castelnuovo, A.; Costanzo, S.; De Curtis, A.; Sarchiapone, M.; Cerletti, C.; Donati, M.B.; de Gaetano, G.; Iacoviello, L.; et al. Lifestyle and biological factors influence the relationship between mental health and low-grade inflammation. *Brain Behav. Immun.* **2020**, *85*, 4–13. [[CrossRef](#)]
151. Astle, W.J.; Elding, H.; Jiang, T.; Allen, D.; Ruklisa, D.; Mann, A.L.; Mead, D.; Bouman, H.; Riveros-Mckay, F.; Kostadima, M.A.; et al. The Allelic Landscape of Human Blood Cell Trait Variation and Links to Common Complex Disease. *Cell* **2016**, *167*, 1415–1429 e1419. [[CrossRef](#)]
152. Bowden, J.; Davey Smith, G.; Burgess, S. Mendelian randomization with invalid instruments: Effect estimation and bias detection through Egger regression. *Int. J. Epidemiol.* **2015**, *44*, 512–525. [[CrossRef](#)]
153. Dudbridge, F. Polygenic Epidemiology. *Genet. Epidemiol.* **2016**, *40*, 268–272. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
154. Hemani, G.; Zheng, J.; Elsworth, B.; Wade, K.H.; Haberland, V.; Baird, D.; Laurin, C.; Burgess, S.; Bowden, J.; Langdon, R.; et al. The MR-Base platform supports systematic causal inference across the human phenome. *eLife* **2018**, *7*. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
155. Davey Smith, G.; Hemani, G. Mendelian randomization: Genetic anchors for causal inference in epidemiological studies. *Hum. Mol. Genet.* **2014**, *23*, R89–R98. [[CrossRef](#)]
156. Wray, N.R.; Ripke, S.; Mattheisen, M.; Trzaskowski, M.; Byrne, E.M.; Abdellaoui, A.; Adams, M.J.; Agerbo, E.; Air, T.M.; Andlauer, T.M.F.; et al. Genome-wide association analyses identify 44 risk variants and refine the genetic architecture of major depression. *Nat. Genet.* **2018**, *50*, 668–681. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
157. Bulik-Sullivan, B.K.; Loh, P.R.; Finucane, H.K.; Ripke, S.; Yang, J.; Schizophrenia Working Group of the Psychiatric Genomics Consortium; Patterson, N.; Daly, M.J.; Price, A.L.; Neale, B.M. LD Score regression distinguishes confounding from polygenicity in genome-wide association studies. *Nat. Genet.* **2015**, *47*, 291–295. [[CrossRef](#)]
158. Bulik-Sullivan, B.; Finucane, H.K.; Anttila, V.; Gusev, A.; Day, F.R.; Loh, P.R.; ReproGen, C.; Psychiatric Genomics, C.; Genetic Consortium for Anorexia Nervosa of the Wellcome Trust Case Control Consortium; Duncan, L.; et al. An atlas of genetic correlations across human diseases and traits. *Nat. Genet.* **2015**, *47*, 1236–1241. [[CrossRef](#)]
159. Gieger, C.; Radhakrishnan, A.; Cvejic, A.; Tang, W.; Porcu, E.; Pistis, G.; Serbanovic-Canic, J.; Elling, U.; Goodall, A.H.; Labrune, Y.; et al. New gene functions in megakaryopoiesis and platelet formation. *Nature* **2011**, *480*, 201–208. [[CrossRef](#)]
160. Panova-Noeva, M.; Schulz, A.; Hermanns, M.I.; Grossmann, V.; Pefani, E.; Spronk, H.M.; Laubert-Reh, D.; Binder, H.; Beutel, M.; Pfeiffer, N.; et al. Sex-specific differences in genetic and nongenetic determinants of mean platelet volume: Results from the Gutenberg Health Study. *Blood* **2016**, *127*, 251–259. [[CrossRef](#)]
161. Kornstein, S.G.; Young, E.A.; Harvey, A.T.; Wisniewski, S.R.; Barkin, J.L.; Thase, M.E.; Trivedi, M.H.; Nierenberg, A.A.; Rush, A.J. The influence of menopause status and postmenopausal use of hormone therapy on presentation of major depression in women. *Menopause* **2010**, *17*, 828–839. [[CrossRef](#)]
162. Young, E.A.; Kornstein, S.G.; Harvey, A.T.; Wisniewski, S.R.; Barkin, J.; Fava, M.; Trivedi, M.H.; Rush, A.J. Influences of hormone-based contraception on depressive symptoms in premenopausal women with major depression. *Psychoneuroendocrinology* **2007**, *32*, 843–853. [[CrossRef](#)]
163. Gold, S.M.; Kohler-Forsberg, O.; Moss-Morris, R.; Mehnert, A.; Miranda, J.J.; Bullinger, M.; Steptoe, A.; Whooley, M.A.; Otte, C. Comorbid depression in medical diseases. *Nat. Rev. Dis. Primers* **2020**, *6*, 69. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
164. Moussavi, S.; Chatterji, S.; Verdes, E.; Tandon, A.; Patel, V.; Ustun, B. Depression, chronic diseases, and decrements in health: Results from the World Health Surveys. *Lancet* **2007**, *370*, 851–858. [[CrossRef](#)]
165. Rutledge, T.; Reis, V.A.; Linke, S.E.; Greenberg, B.H.; Mills, P.J. Depression in heart failure a meta-analytic review of prevalence, intervention effects, and associations with clinical outcomes. *J. Am. Coll. Cardiol.* **2006**, *48*, 1527–1537. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
166. Koyanagi, A.; Kohler-Forsberg, O.; Benros, M.E.; Munk Laursen, T.; Haro, J.M.; Nordentoft, M.; Hjorthoj, C. Mortality in unipolar depression preceding and following chronic somatic diseases. *Acta Psychiatr. Scand.* **2018**, *138*, 500–508. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

167. Momen, N.C.; Plana-Ripoll, O.; Agerbo, E.; Benros, M.E.; Borglum, A.D.; Christensen, M.K.; Dalsgaard, S.; Degenhardt, L.; de Jonge, P.; Debost, J.P.G.; et al. Association between Mental Disorders and Subsequent Medical Conditions. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2020**, *382*, 1721–1731. [[CrossRef](#)]
168. Ransing, R.S.; Gupta, N.; Agrawal, G.; Mahapatro, N. Platelet and Red Blood Cell Indices in Patients with Panic Disorder: A Receiver Operating Characteristic Analysis. *J. Neurosci. Rural. Pract.* **2020**, *11*, 261–266. [[CrossRef](#)]
169. Ransing, R.S.; Patil, B.; Grigo, O. Mean Platelet Volume and Platelet Distribution Width Level in Patients with Panic Disorder. *J. Neurosci. Rural. Pract.* **2017**, *8*, 174–178. [[CrossRef](#)]
170. Bijl, N.; Thys, C.; Wittevrongel, C.; De la Marche, W.; Devriendt, K.; Peeters, H.; Van Geet, C.; Freson, K. Platelet studies in autism spectrum disorder patients and first-degree relatives. *Mol. Autism* **2015**, *6*, 57. [[CrossRef](#)]
171. Akbayram, S.; Gokcen, C.; Karadag, M. Increased of Platelet Indices in Patients with Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder. *Psychiatry Behav. Sci.* **2020**, *10*, 86–89. [[CrossRef](#)]
172. Metin, Ö.; Ray, C.; Shamkhalova, U.; Karci, K.; Tahiroglu, Y.; Kaypakli, Y. The Relationship between platelet activation markers and anxiety symptoms in ADHD. *Klin. Psikofarmakol. Bul.* **2018**, *28* (Suppl. S1), 113.
173. Almis, B.H.; Aksoy, I. Mean platelet volume level in patients with generalized anxiety disorder. *Psychiatry Clin. Psychopharmacol.* **2018**, *28*, 43–47. [[CrossRef](#)]
174. Smolderen, K.G.; Spertus, J.A.; Reid, K.J.; Buchanan, D.M.; Vaccarino, V.; Lichtman, J.H.; Bekelman, D.B.; Chan, P.S. Association of somatic and cognitive depressive symptoms and biomarkers in acute myocardial infarction: Insights from the translational research investigating underlying disparities in acute myocardial infarction patients' health status registry. *Biol. Psychiatry* **2012**, *71*, 22–29. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
175. Kocer, A.; Yaman, A.; Niftaliyev, E.; Duruyen, H.; Eryilmaz, M.; Kocer, E. Assessment of platelet indices in patients with neurodegenerative diseases: Mean platelet volume was increased in patients with Parkinson's disease. *Curr. Gerontol. Geriatr. Res.* **2013**, *2013*, 986254. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
176. Geyik, S.; Yigiter, R.; Akgul, G.P.; Elci, M.; Firat, Y.E. The Relationship Between Parkinson's Disease and Mean Platelet Volume. *Park. Hast. Hareket Bozukluklari Derg.* **2016**, *19*, 31–34.
177. Kokacya, M.H.; Copoglu, U.S.; Kivrak, Y.; Ari, M.; Sahpolat, M.; Ulutas, K.T. Increased mean platelet volume in patients with panic disorder. *Neuropsychiatr. Dis. Treat.* **2015**, *11*, 2629–2633. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
178. Gogcegoz Gul, I.; Eryilmaz, G.; Ozten, E.; Hizli Sayar, G. Decreased mean platelet volume in panic disorder. *Neuropsychiatr. Dis. Treat.* **2014**, *10*, 1665–1669. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
179. Yorbik, O.; Mutlu, C.; Tanju, I.A.; Celik, D.; Ozcan, O. Mean platelet volume in children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. *Med. Hypotheses* **2014**, *82*, 341–345. [[CrossRef](#)]
180. Avcil, S. Evaluation of the neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio, platelet/lymphocyte ratio, and mean platelet volume as inflammatory markers in children with attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder. *Psychiatry Clin. Neurosci.* **2018**, *72*, 522–530. [[CrossRef](#)]
181. Hu, J.; Zhou, W.; Zhou, Z.; Yang, Q.; Han, J.; Yan, Y.; Dong, W. Predictive value of inflammatory indicators for post-stroke depression in patients with ischemic stroke. *Nan Fang Yi Ke Da Xue Xue Bao* **2019**, *39*, 665–671. [[CrossRef](#)]
182. Qiu, H.; Liu, Y.; He, H.; Wu, Y.; He, W.; Huang, G.; He, J. The association between mean platelet volume levels and poststroke depression. *Brain Behav.* **2018**, *8*, e01114. [[CrossRef](#)]
183. Chen, S.H.; Bu, X.L.; Jin, W.S.; Shen, L.L.; Wang, J.; Zhuang, Z.Q.; Zhang, T.; Zeng, F.; Yao, X.Q.; Zhou, H.D.; et al. Altered peripheral profile of blood cells in Alzheimer disease: A hospital-based case-control study. *Medicine (Baltimore)* **2017**, *96*, e6843. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
184. Asoglu, M.; Aslan, M.; Imre, O.; Kivrak, Y.; Akil, O.; Savik, E.; Buyukaslan, H.; Fedai, U.; Altindag, A. Mean platelet volume and red cell distribution width levels in initial evaluation of panic disorder. *Neuropsychiatr. Dis. Treat.* **2016**, *12*, 2435–2438. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
185. Naghipour Hamzekolaei, M.; Jafarisani, M.; Farajzadeh, A.; Aghayan, S.S.; Atashi, A.; Yarmohammadi, M.; Sadeghi, I.; Tashakori, M. Changes in mean platelet volume and hematologic indices in patients with panic disorder due to oxidative stress. *Brain Behav.* **2020**, *10*, e01569. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
186. Fluegge, K.; Fluegge, K. Environmental factors influencing the link between childhood ADHD and risk of adult coronary artery disease. *Med. Hypotheses* **2018**, *110*, 83–85. [[CrossRef](#)]
187. Liang, Q.C.; Jin, D.; Li, Y.; Wang, R.T. Mean platelet volume and platelet distribution width in vascular dementia and Alzheimer's disease. *Platelets* **2014**, *25*, 433–438. [[CrossRef](#)]

188. Wang, R.T.; Jin, D.; Li, Y.; Liang, Q.C. Decreased mean platelet volume and platelet distribution width are associated with mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease. *J. Psychiatr. Res.* **2013**, *47*, 644–649. [[CrossRef](#)]
189. Arora, R.C.; Meltzer, H.Y. Increased serotonin₂ (5-HT₂) receptor binding as measured by 3H-lysergic acid diethylamide (3H-LSD) in the blood platelets of depressed patients. *Life Sci.* **1989**, *44*, 725–734. [[CrossRef](#)]
190. Hrdina, P.D.; Bakish, D.; Ravindran, A.; Chudzik, J.; Cavazzoni, P.; Lapierre, Y.D. Platelet serotonergic indices in major depression: Up-regulation of 5-HT_{2A} receptors unchanged by antidepressant treatment. *Psychiatry Res.* **1997**, *66*, 73–85. [[CrossRef](#)]
191. Williams, M.S.; Ziegelstein, R.C.; McCann, U.D.; Gould, N.F.; Ashvetiya, T.; Vaidya, D. Platelet Serotonin Signaling in Patients With Cardiovascular Disease and Comorbid Depression. *Psychosom. Med.* **2019**, *81*, 352–362. [[CrossRef](#)]
192. Nemeroff, C.B.; Knight, D.L.; Franks, J.; Craighead, W.E.; Krishnan, K.R. Further studies on platelet serotonin transporter binding in depression. *Am. J. Psychiatry* **1994**, *151*, 1623–1625. [[CrossRef](#)]
193. Kumar, A.M.; Kumar, M.; Sevush, S.; Ruiz, J.; Eisdorfer, C. Serotonin uptake and its kinetics in platelets of women with Alzheimer's disease. *Psychiatry Res.* **1995**, *59*, 145–150. [[CrossRef](#)]
194. Koren, P.; Diver-Haber, A.; Adunsky, A.; Rabinowitz, M.; Hershkowitz, M. Uptake of serotonin into platelets of senile dementia of the Alzheimer type patients. *J. Gerontol.* **1993**, *48*, B93–B96. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
195. Suranyi-Cadotte, B.E.; Gauthier, S.; Lafaille, F.; DeFlores, S.; Dam, T.V.; Nair, N.P.; Quirion, R. Platelet 3H-imipramine binding distinguishes depression from Alzheimer dementia. *Life Sci.* **1985**, *37*, 2305–2311. [[CrossRef](#)]
196. Inestrosa, N.C.; Alarcon, R.; Arriagada, J.; Donoso, A.; Alvarez, J. Platelet of Alzheimer patients: Increased counts and subnormal uptake and accumulation of [¹⁴C]5-hydroxytryptamine. *Neurosci. Lett.* **1993**, *163*, 8–10. [[CrossRef](#)]
197. Tukiainen, E.; Wikstrom, J.; Kilpelainen, H. Uptake of 5-hydroxytryptamine by blood platelets in Huntington's chorea and Alzheimer type of presenile dementia. *Med. Biol.* **1981**, *59*, 116–120. [[PubMed](#)]
198. Arora, R.C.; Emery, O.B.; Meltzer, H.Y. Serotonin uptake in the blood platelets of Alzheimer's disease patients. *Neurology* **1991**, *41*, 1307–1309. [[CrossRef](#)]
199. Schins, A.; Hamulyak, K.; Scharpe, S.; Lousberg, R.; Van Melle, J.; Crijns, H.; Honig, A. Whole blood serotonin and platelet activation in depressed post-myocardial infarction patients. *Life Sci.* **2004**, *76*, 637–650. [[CrossRef](#)]
200. Meszaros, Z.; Borcsiczky, D.; Mate, M.; Tarcali, J.; Szombathy, T.; Tekes, K.; Magyar, K. Platelet MAO-B activity and serotonin content in patients with dementia: Effect of age, medication, and disease. *Neurochem. Res.* **1998**, *23*, 863–868. [[CrossRef](#)]
201. Kumar, A.M.; Sevush, S.; Kumar, M.; Ruiz, J.; Eisdorfer, C. Peripheral serotonin in Alzheimer's disease. *Neuropsychobiology* **1995**, *32*, 9–12. [[CrossRef](#)]
202. Mimica, N.; Muck-Seler, D.; Pivac, N.; Mustapic, M.; Dezeljin, M.; Stipcevic, T.; Presecki, P.; Radonic, E.; Folnegovic-Smalc, V. Platelet serotonin and monoamine oxidase in Alzheimer's disease with psychotic features. *Coll. Antropol.* **2008**, *32* (Suppl. 1), 119–122.
203. Muck-Seler, D.; Presecki, P.; Mimica, N.; Mustapic, M.; Pivac, N.; Babic, A.; Nedic, G.; Folnegovic-Smalc, V. Platelet serotonin concentration and monoamine oxidase type B activity in female patients in early, middle and late phase of Alzheimer's disease. *Prog Neuropsychopharmacol. Biol. Psychiatry* **2009**, *33*, 1226–1231. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
204. Dupuis, L.; Spreux-Varoquaux, O.; Bensimon, G.; Jullien, P.; Lacomblez, L.; Salachas, F.; Bruneteau, G.; Pradat, P.F.; Loeffler, J.P.; Meininger, V. Platelet serotonin level predicts survival in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *PLoS ONE* **2010**, *5*, e13346. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
205. Steventon, G.B.; Sturman, S.G.; Heafield, M.T.; Waring, R.H.; Napier, J.; Williams, A.C. Platelet monoamine oxidase-B activity in Parkinson's disease. *J. Neural. Transm. Park. Dis. Dement. Sect.* **1989**, *1*, 255–261. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
206. Husain, M.; Shukla, R.; Dikshit, M.; Maheshwari, P.K.; Nag, D.; Srimal, R.C.; Seth, P.K.; Khanna, V.K. Altered platelet monoamine oxidase-B activity in idiopathic Parkinson's disease. *Neurochem Res.* **2009**, *34*, 1427–1432. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
207. Jakubauskiene, E.; Janaviciute, V.; Peculiene, I.; Soderkvist, P.; Kanopka, A. G/A polymorphism in intronic sequence affects the processing of MAO-B gene in patients with Parkinson disease. *FEBS Lett.* **2012**, *586*, 3698–3704. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

208. Zhou, G.; Miura, Y.; Shoji, H.; Yamada, S.; Matsuishi, T. Platelet monoamine oxidase B and plasma beta-phenylethylamine in Parkinson's disease. *J. Neurol. Neurosurg. Psychiatry* **2001**, *70*, 229–231. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
209. Gotz, M.E.; Gerstner, A.; Harth, R.; Dirr, A.; Janetzky, B.; Kuhn, W.; Riederer, P.; Gerlach, M. Altered redox state of platelet coenzyme Q10 in Parkinson's disease. *J. Neural. Transm. (Vienna)* **2000**, *107*, 41–48. [[CrossRef](#)]
210. Zellner, M.; Baureder, M.; Rappold, E.; Bugert, P.; Kotzailias, N.; Babeluk, R.; Baumgartner, R.; Attems, J.; Gerner, C.; Jellinger, K.; et al. Comparative platelet proteome analysis reveals an increase of monoamine oxidase-B protein expression in Alzheimer's disease but not in non-demented Parkinson's disease patients. *J. Proteomics* **2012**, *75*, 2080–2092. [[CrossRef](#)]
211. Benecke, R.; Strumper, P.; Weiss, H. Electron transfer complexes I and IV of platelets are abnormal in Parkinson's disease but normal in Parkinson-plus syndromes. *Brain* **1993**, *116 Pt 6*, 1451–1463. [[CrossRef](#)]
212. Haas, R.H.; Nasirian, F.; Nakano, K.; Ward, D.; Pay, M.; Hill, R.; Shults, C.W. Low platelet mitochondrial complex I and complex II/III activity in early untreated Parkinson's disease. *Ann. Neurol.* **1995**, *37*, 714–722. [[CrossRef](#)]
213. Parker, W.D., Jr.; Parks, J.K.; Swerdlow, R.H. Complex I deficiency in Parkinson's disease frontal cortex. *Brain Res.* **2008**, *1189*, 215–218. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
214. Bronstein, J.M.; Paul, K.; Yang, L.; Haas, R.H.; Shults, C.W.; Le, T.; Ritz, B. Platelet mitochondrial activity and pesticide exposure in early Parkinson's disease. *Mov. Disord.* **2015**, *30*, 862–866. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
215. Hanagasi, H.A.; Ayribas, D.; Baysal, K.; Emre, M. Mitochondrial complex I, II/III, and IV activities in familial and sporadic Parkinson's disease. *Int. J. Neurosci.* **2005**, *115*, 479–493. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
216. Shrivastava, M.; Das, T.K.; Behari, M.; Pati, U.; Vivekanandhan, S. Ultrastructural variations in platelets and platelet mitochondria: A novel feature in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Ultrastruct. Pathol.* **2011**, *35*, 52–59. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
217. Sevush, S.; Jy, W.; Horstman, L.L.; Mao, W.W.; Kolodny, L.; Ahn, Y.S. Platelet activation in Alzheimer disease. *Arch. Neurol.* **1998**, *55*, 530–536. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
218. Kuijpers, P.M.; Hamulyak, K.; Strik, J.J.; Wellens, H.J.; Honig, A. Beta-thromboglobulin and platelet factor 4 levels in post-myocardial infarction patients with major depression. *Psychiatry Res.* **2002**, *109*, 207–210. [[CrossRef](#)]
219. Serebruany, V.L.; Glassman, A.H.; Malinin, A.I.; Sane, D.C.; Finkel, M.S.; Krishnan, R.R.; Atar, D.; Lekht, V.; O'Connor, C.M. Enhanced platelet/endothelial activation in depressed patients with acute coronary syndromes: Evidence from recent clinical trials. *Blood Coagul. Fibrinolysis* **2003**, *14*, 563–567. [[CrossRef](#)]
220. Laghrissi-Thode, F.; Wagner, W.R.; Pollock, B.G.; Johnson, P.C.; Finkel, M.S. Elevated platelet factor 4 and beta-thromboglobulin plasma levels in depressed patients with ischemic heart disease. *Biol. Psychiatry* **1997**, *42*, 290–295. [[CrossRef](#)]
221. Pollock, B.G.; Laghrissi-Thode, F.; Wagner, W.R. Evaluation of platelet activation in depressed patients with ischemic heart disease after paroxetine or nortriptyline treatment. *J. Clin. Psychopharmacol.* **2000**, *20*, 137–140. [[CrossRef](#)]
222. Barth, J.; Schumacher, M.; Herrmann-Lingen, C. Depression as a risk factor for mortality in patients with coronary heart disease: A meta-analysis. *Psychosom. Med.* **2004**, *66*, 802–813. [[CrossRef](#)]
223. Ahto, M.; Isoaho, R.; Puolijoki, H.; Vahlberg, T.; Kivela, S.L. Stronger symptoms of depression predict high coronary heart disease mortality in older men and women. *Int. J. Geriatr. Psychiatry* **2007**, *22*, 757–763. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
224. Gump, B.B.; Matthews, K.A.; Eberly, L.E.; Chang, Y.F.; Group, M.R. Depressive symptoms and mortality in men: Results from the Multiple Risk Factor Intervention Trial. *Stroke* **2005**, *36*, 98–102. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
225. Lesperance, F.; Frasure-Smith, N.; Talajic, M.; Bourassa, M.G. Five-year risk of cardiac mortality in relation to initial severity and one-year changes in depression symptoms after myocardial infarction. *Circulation* **2002**, *105*, 1049–1053. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
226. Jiang, W.; Alexander, J.; Christopher, E.; Kuchibhatla, M.; Gauden, L.H.; Cuffe, M.S.; Blazing, M.A.; Davenport, C.; Califf, R.M.; Krishnan, R.R.; et al. Relationship of depression to increased risk of mortality and rehospitalization in patients with congestive heart failure. *Arch. Intern. Med.* **2001**, *161*, 1849–1856. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
227. Frasure-Smith, N.; Lesperance, F.; Talajic, M. Depression following myocardial infarction. Impact on 6-month survival. *JAMA* **1993**, *270*, 1819–1825. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

228. Frasure-Smith, N.; Lesperance, F.; Talajic, M. Depression and 18-month prognosis after myocardial infarction. *Circulation* **1995**, *91*, 999–1005. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
229. Junger, J.; Schellberg, D.; Muller-Tasch, T.; Raupp, G.; Zugck, C.; Haunstetter, A.; Zipfel, S.; Herzog, W.; Haass, M. Depression increasingly predicts mortality in the course of congestive heart failure. *Eur. J. Heart. Fail.* **2005**, *7*, 261–267. [[CrossRef](#)]
230. Sherwood, A.; Blumenthal, J.A.; Trivedi, R.; Johnson, K.S.; O'Connor, C.M.; Adams, K.F., Jr.; Dupree, C.S.; Waugh, R.A.; Bensimhon, D.R.; Gaulden, L.; et al. Relationship of depression to death or hospitalization in patients with heart failure. *Arch. Intern. Med.* **2007**, *167*, 367–373. [[CrossRef](#)]
231. Ahern, D.K.; Gorkin, L.; Anderson, J.L.; Tierney, C.; Hallstrom, A.; Ewart, C.; Capone, R.J.; Schron, E.; Kornfeld, D.; Herd, J.A.; et al. Biobehavioral variables and mortality or cardiac arrest in the Cardiac Arrhythmia Pilot Study (CAPS). *Am. J. Cardiol.* **1990**, *66*, 59–62. [[CrossRef](#)]
232. Bush, D.E.; Ziegelstein, R.C.; Tayback, M.; Richter, D.; Stevens, S.; Zahalsky, H.; Fauerbach, J.A. Even minimal symptoms of depression increase mortality risk after acute myocardial infarction. *Am. J. Cardiol.* **2001**, *88*, 337–341. [[CrossRef](#)]
233. Shah, A.J.; Ghasemzadeh, N.; Zaragoza-Macias, E.; Patel, R.; Eapen, D.J.; Neeland, I.J.; Pimple, P.M.; Zafari, A.M.; Quyyumi, A.A.; Vaccarino, V. Sex and age differences in the association of depression with obstructive coronary artery disease and adverse cardiovascular events. *J. Am. Heart Assoc.* **2014**, *3*, e000741. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
234. Van Dijk, M.R.; Utens, E.M.; Dulfer, K.; Al-Quezweny, M.N.; van Geuns, R.J.; Daemen, J.; van Domburg, R.T. Depression and anxiety symptoms as predictors of mortality in PCI patients at 10 years of follow-up. *Eur. J. Prev. Cardiol.* **2016**, *23*, 552–558. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
235. Wulsin, L.R.; Evans, J.C.; Vasan, R.S.; Murabito, J.M.; Kelly-Hayes, M.; Benjamin, E.J. Depressive symptoms, coronary heart disease, and overall mortality in the Framingham Heart Study. *Psychosom. Med.* **2005**, *67*, 697–702. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
236. Gialluisi, A.; Costanzo, S.; Di Castelnuovo, A.; Bonaccio, M.; Bracone, F.; Magnacca, S.; De Curtis, A.; Cerletti, C.; Donati, M.B.; De Gaetano, G.; et al. Moli-sani Study Investigators. Combined influence of depression severity and low-grade inflammation on incident hospitalization and mortality risk in Italian adults: Depression, inflammation and risk of clinical events. *J. Affect. Disord.* **2021**, *279*, 173–182. [[CrossRef](#)]
237. Nicholson, A.; Kuper, H.; Hemingway, H. Depression as an aetiologic and prognostic factor in coronary heart disease: A meta-analysis of 6362 events among 146 538 participants in 54 observational studies. *Eur. Heart J.* **2006**, *27*, 2763–2774. [[CrossRef](#)]
238. Ariyo, A.A.; Haan, M.; Tangen, C.M.; Rutledge, J.C.; Cushman, M.; Dobs, A.; Furberg, C.D. Depressive symptoms and risks of coronary heart disease and mortality in elderly Americans. Cardiovascular Health Study Collaborative Research Group. *Circulation* **2000**, *102*, 1773–1779. [[CrossRef](#)]
239. Ford, D.E.; Mead, L.A.; Chang, P.P.; Cooper-Patrick, L.; Wang, N.Y.; Klag, M.J. Depression is a risk factor for coronary artery disease in men: The precursors study. *Arch. Intern. Med.* **1998**, *158*, 1422–1426. [[CrossRef](#)]
240. Penninx, B.W.; Beekman, A.T.; Honig, A.; Deeg, D.J.; Schoevers, R.A.; van Eijk, J.T.; van Tilburg, W. Depression and cardiac mortality: Results from a community-based longitudinal study. *Arch. Gen. Psychiatry* **2001**, *58*, 221–227. [[CrossRef](#)]
241. Carney, R.M.; Jaffe, A.S. Treatment of depression following acute myocardial infarction. *JAMA* **2002**, *288*, 750–751. [[CrossRef](#)]
242. Musselman, D.L.; Evans, D.L.; Nemeroff, C.B. The relationship of depression to cardiovascular disease: Epidemiology, biology, and treatment. *Arch. Gen. Psychiatry* **1998**, *55*, 580–592. [[CrossRef](#)]
243. O'Connor, C.M.; Gurbel, P.A.; Serebruany, V.L. Depression and ischemic heart disease. *Am. Heart J.* **2000**, *140*, 63–69. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
244. Fielding, R. Depression and acute myocardial infarction: A review and reinterpretation. *Soc. Sci. Med.* **1991**, *32*, 1017–1028. [[CrossRef](#)]
245. Rudisch, B.; Nemeroff, C.B. Epidemiology of comorbid coronary artery disease and depression. *Biol. Psychiatry* **2003**, *54*, 227–240. [[CrossRef](#)]
246. Schleifer, S.J.; Macari-Hinson, M.M.; Coyle, D.A.; Slater, W.R.; Kahn, M.; Gorlin, R.; Zucker, H.D. The nature and course of depression following myocardial infarction. *Arch. Intern. Med.* **1989**, *149*, 1785–1789. [[CrossRef](#)]

247. Eaton, W.W.F.J.; Armenian, H.K. The consequences of psychopathology in the Baltimore Epidemiologic Catchment Area Follow-up. In *Medical and Psychiatric Co-Morbidity over the Lifespan*; American Psychiatric Publishing: Washington, DC, USA, 2006; pp. 21–38.
248. Pan, A.; Sun, Q.; Okereke, O.I.; Rexrode, K.M.; Hu, F.B. Depression and risk of stroke morbidity and mortality: A meta-analysis and systematic review. *JAMA* **2011**, *306*, 1241–1249. [[CrossRef](#)]
249. Ayerbe, L.; Ayis, S.; Wolfe, C.D.; Rudd, A.G. Natural history, predictors and outcomes of depression after stroke: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Br. J. Psychiatry* **2013**, *202*, 14–21. [[CrossRef](#)]
250. Hackett, M.L.; Pickles, K. Part I: Frequency of depression after stroke: An updated systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *Int. J. Stroke* **2014**, *9*, 1017–1025. [[CrossRef](#)]
251. Penninx, B.W.; Milaneschi, Y.; Lamers, F.; Vogelzangs, N. Understanding the somatic consequences of depression: Biological mechanisms and the role of depression symptom profile. *BMC Med.* **2013**, *11*, 129. [[CrossRef](#)]
252. Whooley, M.A.; de Jonge, P.; Vittinghoff, E.; Otte, C.; Moos, R.; Carney, R.M.; Ali, S.; Dowray, S.; Na, B.; Feldman, M.D.; et al. Depressive symptoms, health behaviors, and risk of cardiovascular events in patients with coronary heart disease. *JAMA* **2008**, *300*, 2379–2388. [[CrossRef](#)]
253. Peterson, J.C.; Charlson, M.E.; Wells, M.T.; Altemus, M. Depression, coronary artery disease, and physical activity: How much exercise is enough? *Clin. Ther.* **2014**, *36*, 1518–1530. [[CrossRef](#)]
254. Ziegelstein, R.C.; Parakh, K.; Sakhuja, A.; Bhat, U. Platelet function in patients with major depression. *Intern. Med. J.* **2009**, *39*, 38–43. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
255. Nemeroff, C.B.; Musselman, D.L. Are platelets the link between depression and ischemic heart disease? *Am. Heart J.* **2000**, *140*, 57–62. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
256. Bruce, E.C.; Musselman, D.L. Depression, alterations in platelet function, and ischemic heart disease. *Psychosom. Med.* **2005**, *67* (Suppl. 1), S34–S36. [[CrossRef](#)]
257. Musselman, D.L.; Marzec, U.; Davidoff, M.; Manatunga, A.K.; Gao, F.; Reemsnyder, A.; Duggirala, S.; Larsen, H.; Taylor, R.W.; Hanson, S.; et al. Platelet activation and secretion in patients with major depression, thoracic aortic atherosclerosis, or renal dialysis treatment. *Depress. Anxiety* **2002**, *15*, 91–101. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
258. Skop, B.P.; Brown, T.M. Potential vascular and bleeding complications of treatment with selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors. *Psychosomatics* **1996**, *37*, 12–16. [[CrossRef](#)]
259. Miyata, K.; Shimokawa, H.; Higo, T.; Yamawaki, T.; Katsumata, N.; Kandabashi, T.; Tanaka, E.; Takamura, Y.; Yogo, K.; Egashira, K.; et al. Sarpogrelate, a selective 5-HT_{2A} serotonergic receptor antagonist, inhibits serotonin-induced coronary artery spasm in a porcine model. *J. Cardiovasc. Pharmacol.* **2000**, *35*, 294–301. [[CrossRef](#)]
260. Vikenes, K.; Farstad, M.; Nordrehaug, J.E. Serotonin is associated with coronary artery disease and cardiac events. *Circulation* **1999**, *100*, 483–489. [[CrossRef](#)]
261. Gehi, A.; Musselman, D.; Otte, C.; Bruce Royster, E.; Ali, S.; Whooley, M.A. Depression and platelet activation in outpatients with stable coronary heart disease: Findings from the Heart and Soul Study. *Psychiatry Res.* **2010**, *175*, 200–204. [[CrossRef](#)]
262. Zafar, M.U.; Paz-Yepes, M.; Shimbo, D.; Vilahur, G.; Burg, M.M.; Chaplin, W.; Fuster, V.; Davidson, K.W.; Badimon, J.J. Anxiety is a better predictor of platelet reactivity in coronary artery disease patients than depression. *Eur. Heart J.* **2010**, *31*, 1573–1582. [[CrossRef](#)]
263. Serebruany, V.L.; Suckow, R.F.; Cooper, T.B.; O'Connor, C.M.; Malinin, A.I.; Krishnan, K.R.; van Zyl, L.T.; Lekht, V.; Glassman, A.H.; Sertraline Antidepressant Heart Attack Randomized Trial. Relationship between release of platelet/endothelial biomarkers and plasma levels of sertraline and N-desmethylsertraline in acute coronary syndrome patients receiving SSRI treatment for depression. *Am. J. Psychiatry* **2005**, *162*, 1165–1170. [[CrossRef](#)]
264. Serebruany, V.L.; Gurbel, P.A.; O'Connor, C.M. Platelet inhibition by sertraline and N-desmethylsertraline: A possible missing link between depression, coronary events, and mortality benefits of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors. *Pharmacol. Res.* **2001**, *43*, 453–462. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
265. Pizzi, C.; Rutjes, A.W.; Costa, G.M.; Fontana, F.; Mezzetti, A.; Manzoli, L. Meta-analysis of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors in patients with depression and coronary heart disease. *Am. J. Cardiol.* **2011**, *107*, 972–979. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
266. Von Kanel, R. Platelet hyperactivity in clinical depression and the beneficial effect of antidepressant drug treatment: How strong is the evidence? *Acta Psychiatr. Scand.* **2004**, *110*, 163–177. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

267. Ahrens, T.; Frankhauser, P.; Lederbogen, F.; Deuschle, M. Effect of single-dose sertraline on the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal system, autonomic nervous system, and platelet function. *J. Clin. Psychopharmacol.* **2007**, *27*, 602–606. [[CrossRef](#)]
268. Cassidy, E.M.; Walsh, M.T.; O'Connor, R.; Condren, R.M.; Ryan, M.; O'Keane, V.; Kenny, D.; Dinan, T. Platelet surface glycoprotein expression in post-stroke depression: A preliminary study. *Psychiatry Res.* **2003**, *118*, 175–181. [[CrossRef](#)]
269. Shimokhina, N.Y.; Savchenko, A.A.; Petrova, M.M. Peculiarities of Platelet Metabolism in Patients with Acute Coronary Syndrome with Anxiety-Depressive Disorders and Informativity of Enzymes in the Forecast of Development of Cardiovascular Complications. *Pharmaceuticals* **2020**, *13*, 169. [[CrossRef](#)]
270. Huang, G.; Chen, H.; Wang, Q.; Hong, X.; Hu, P.; Xiao, M.; Shu, M.; He, J. High platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio are associated with post-stroke depression. *J. Affect. Disord.* **2019**, *246*, 105–111. [[CrossRef](#)]
271. Selkoe, D.J. Alzheimer's disease is a synaptic failure. *Science* **2002**, *298*, 789–791. [[CrossRef](#)]
272. Wojsiat, J.; Laskowska-Kaszub, K.; Mietelska-Porowska, A.; Wojda, U. Search for Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in blood cells: Hypotheses-driven approach. *Biomark. Med.* **2017**, *11*, 917–931. [[CrossRef](#)]
273. Leiter, O.; Walker, T.L. Platelets in Neurodegenerative Conditions-Friend or Foe? *Front. Immunol.* **2020**, *11*, 747. [[CrossRef](#)]
274. Jaremo, P.; Milovanovic, M.; Buller, C.; Nilsson, S.; Winblad, B. P-selectin paradox and dementia of the Alzheimer type: Circulating P-selectin is increased but platelet-bound P-selectin after agonist provocation is compromised. *Scand. J. Clin. Lab. Invest.* **2013**, *73*, 170–174. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
275. Prodan, C.I.; Ross, E.D.; Vincent, A.S.; Dale, G.L. Differences in coated-platelet production between frontotemporal dementia and Alzheimer disease. *Alzheimer Dis. Assoc. Disord.* **2009**, *23*, 234–237. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
276. Prodan, C.I.; Ross, E.D.; Vincent, A.S.; Dale, G.L. Rate of progression in Alzheimer's disease correlates with coated-platelet levels—a longitudinal study. *Transl. Res.* **2008**, *152*, 99–102. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
277. Prodan, C.I.; Ross, E.D.; Vincent, A.S.; Dale, G.L. Coated-platelets correlate with disease progression in Alzheimer disease. *J. Neurol.* **2007**, *254*, 548–549. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
278. Prodan, C.I.; Ross, E.D.; Stoner, J.A.; Cowan, L.D.; Vincent, A.S.; Dale, G.L. Coated-platelet levels and progression from mild cognitive impairment to Alzheimer disease. *Neurology* **2011**, *76*, 247–252. [[CrossRef](#)]
279. Meltzer, C.C.; Smith, G.; DeKosky, S.T.; Pollock, B.G.; Mathis, C.A.; Moore, R.Y.; Kupfer, D.J.; Reynolds, C.F., 3rd. Serotonin in aging, late-life depression, and Alzheimer's disease: The emerging role of functional imaging. *Neuropsychopharmacology* **1998**, *18*, 407–430. [[CrossRef](#)]
280. Veitinger, M.; Varga, B.; Guterres, S.B.; Zellner, M. Platelets, a reliable source for peripheral Alzheimer's disease biomarkers? *Acta Neuropathol. Commun.* **2014**, *2*, 65. [[CrossRef](#)]
281. Schmaier, A.H. Alzheimer disease is in part a thrombohemorrhagic disorder. *J. Thromb. Haemost.* **2016**, *14*, 991–994. [[CrossRef](#)]
282. Inyushin, M.Y.; Sanabria, P.; Rojas, L.; Kucheryavykh, Y.; Kucheryavykh, L. Abeta Peptide Originated from Platelets Promises New Strategy in Anti-Alzheimer's Drug Development. *Biomed. Res. Int.* **2017**, *2017*, 3948360. [[CrossRef](#)]
283. Canobbio, I.; Visconte, C.; Oliviero, B.; Guidetti, G.; Zara, M.; Pula, G.; Torti, M. Increased platelet adhesion and thrombus formation in a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease. *Cell Signal.* **2016**, *28*, 1863–1871. [[CrossRef](#)]
284. Di Luca, M.; Pastorino, L.; Cattabeni, F.; Zanardi, R.; Scarone, S.; Racagni, G.; Smeraldi, E.; Perez, J. Abnormal pattern of platelet APP isoforms in Alzheimer disease and Down syndrome. *Arch. Neurol.* **1996**, *53*, 1162–1166. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
285. Borroni, B.; Colciaghi, F.; Caltagirone, C.; Rozzini, L.; Broglio, L.; Cattabeni, F.; Di Luca, M.; Padovani, A. Platelet amyloid precursor protein abnormalities in mild cognitive impairment predict conversion to dementia of Alzheimer type: A 2-year follow-up study. *Arch. Neurol.* **2003**, *60*, 1740–1744. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
286. Di Luca, M.; Pastorino, L.; Bianchetti, A.; Perez, J.; Vignolo, L.A.; Lenzi, G.L.; Trabucchi, M.; Cattabeni, F.; Padovani, A. Differential level of platelet amyloid beta precursor protein isoforms: An early marker for Alzheimer disease. *Arch. Neurol.* **1998**, *55*, 1195–1200. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
287. Padovani, A.; Pastorino, L.; Borroni, B.; Colciaghi, F.; Rozzini, L.; Monastero, R.; Perez, J.; Pettenati, C.; Mussi, M.; Parrinello, G.; et al. Amyloid precursor protein in platelets: A peripheral marker for the diagnosis of sporadic AD. *Neurology* **2001**, *57*, 2243–2248. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

288. Rosenberg, R.N.; Baskin, F.; Fosmire, J.A.; Risser, R.; Adams, P.; Svetlik, D.; Honig, L.S.; Cullum, C.M.; Weiner, M.F. Altered amyloid protein processing in platelets of patients with Alzheimer disease. *Arch. Neurol.* **1997**, *54*, 139–144. [[CrossRef](#)]
289. Colciaghi, F.; Marcello, E.; Borroni, B.; Zimmermann, M.; Caltagirone, C.; Cattabeni, F.; Padovani, A.; Di Luca, M. Platelet APP, ADAM 10 and BACE alterations in the early stages of Alzheimer disease. *Neurology* **2004**, *62*, 498–501. [[CrossRef](#)]
290. Baskin, F.; Rosenberg, R.N.; Iyer, L.; Hynan, L.; Cullum, C.M. Platelet APP isoform ratios correlate with declining cognition in AD. *Neurology* **2000**, *54*, 1907–1909. [[CrossRef](#)]
291. Borroni, B.; Agosti, C.; Marcello, E.; Di Luca, M.; Padovani, A. Blood cell markers in Alzheimer Disease: Amyloid Precursor Protein form ratio in platelets. *Exp. Gerontol.* **2010**, *45*, 53–56. [[CrossRef](#)]
292. Gialluisi, A.; Reccia, M.G.; Tirozzi, A.; Nutile, T.; Lombardi, A.; De Sanctis, C.; International Parkinson's Disease Genomic, C.; Varanese, S.; Pietracupa, S.; Modugno, N.; et al. Whole Exome Sequencing Study of Parkinson Disease and Related Endophenotypes in the Italian Population. *Front. Neurol.* **2019**, *10*, 1362. [[CrossRef](#)]
293. Jansen, I.E.; Savage, J.E.; Watanabe, K.; Bryois, J.; Williams, D.M.; Steinberg, S.; Sealock, J.; Karlsson, I.K.; Hagg, S.; Athanasiu, L.; et al. Genome-wide meta-analysis identifies new loci and functional pathways influencing Alzheimer's disease risk. *Nat. Genet.* **2019**, *51*, 404–413. [[CrossRef](#)]
294. Tirozzi, A.; Izzi, B.; Noro, F.; Marotta, A.; Gianfagna, F.; Hoylaerts, M.F.; Cerletti, C.; Donati, M.B.; De Gaetano, G.; Iacoviello, L.; et al. Assessing Genetic Overlap Between Platelet Parameters and Neurodegenerative Disorders. *Front. Immunol.* **2020**, *11*, 02127. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
295. Keane, P.C.; Kurzawa, M.; Blain, P.G.; Morris, C.M. Mitochondrial dysfunction in Parkinson's disease. *Parkinsons. Dis.* **2011**, *2011*, 716871. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
296. Lim, K.M.; Kim, H.H.; Bae, O.N.; Noh, J.Y.; Kim, K.Y.; Kim, S.H.; Chung, S.M.; Shin, S.; Kim, H.Y.; Chung, J.H. Inhibition of platelet aggregation by 1-methyl-4-phenyl pyridinium ion (MPP+) through ATP depletion: Evidence for the reduced platelet activities in Parkinson's disease. *Platelets* **2009**, *20*, 163–170. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
297. Nalls, M.A.; Blauwendraat, C.; Vallerga, C.L.; Heilbron, K.; Bandres-Ciga, S.; Chang, D.; Tan, M.; Kia, D.A.; Noyce, A.J.; Xue, A.; et al. Identification of novel risk loci, causal insights, and heritable risk for Parkinson's disease: A meta-analysis of genome-wide association studies. *Lancet Neurol.* **2019**, *18*, 1091–1102. [[CrossRef](#)]
298. Aarsland, D.; Creese, B.; Politis, M.; Chaudhuri, K.R.; Ffytche, D.H.; Weintraub, D.; Ballard, C. Cognitive decline in Parkinson disease. *Nat. Rev. Neurol.* **2017**, *13*, 217–231. [[CrossRef](#)]
299. Roos, E.; Mariosa, D.; Ingre, C.; Lundholm, C.; Wirdefeldt, K.; Roos, P.M.; Fang, F. Depression in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Neurology* **2016**, *86*, 2271–2277. [[CrossRef](#)]
300. Mathews, D.C.; Henter, I.D.; Zarate, C.A. Targeting the glutamatergic system to treat major depressive disorder: Rationale and progress to date. *Drugs* **2012**, *72*, 1313–1333. [[CrossRef](#)]
301. Ferrarese, C.; Sala, G.; Riva, R.; Begni, B.; Zoia, C.; Tremolizzo, L.; Galimberti, G.; Millul, A.; Bastone, A.; Mennini, T.; et al. Decreased platelet glutamate uptake in patients with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Neurology* **2001**, *56*, 270–272. [[CrossRef](#)]
302. Rothstein, J.D.; Van Kammen, M.; Levey, A.I.; Martin, L.J.; Kuncl, R.W. Selective loss of glial glutamate transporter GLT-1 in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Ann. Neurol.* **1995**, *38*, 73–84. [[CrossRef](#)]
303. Bos, I.W.; Hoogland, G.; Meine Jansen, C.F.; Willigen, G.; Spierenburg, H.A.; van den Berg, L.H.; de Graan, P.N. Increased glutamine synthetase but normal EAAT2 expression in platelets of ALS patients. *Neurochem. Int.* **2006**, *48*, 306–311. [[CrossRef](#)]
304. Hishizawa, M.; Yamashita, H.; Akizuki, M.; Urushitani, M.; Takahashi, R. TDP-43 levels are higher in platelets from patients with sporadic amyotrophic lateral sclerosis than in healthy controls. *Neurochem. Int.* **2019**, *124*, 41–45. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
305. Ling, S.C.; Polymenidou, M.; Cleveland, D.W. Converging mechanisms in ALS and FTD: Disrupted RNA and protein homeostasis. *Neuron* **2013**, *79*, 416–438. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
306. Neumann, M.; Sampathu, D.M.; Kwong, L.K.; Truax, A.C.; Micsenyi, M.C.; Chou, T.T.; Bruce, J.; Schuck, T.; Grossman, M.; Clark, C.M.; et al. Ubiquitinated TDP-43 in frontotemporal lobar degeneration and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Science* **2006**, *314*, 130–133. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
307. Ballenger, J.C. Remission rates in patients with anxiety disorders treated with paroxetine. *J. Clin. Psychiatry* **2004**, *65*, 1696–1707. [[CrossRef](#)]

308. Strike, P.C.; Magid, K.; Brydon, L.; Edwards, S.; McEwan, J.R.; Steptoe, A. Exaggerated platelet and hemodynamic reactivity to mental stress in men with coronary artery disease. *Psychosom. Med.* **2004**, *66*, 492–500. [[CrossRef](#)]
309. Levine, S.P.; Towell, B.L.; Suarez, A.M.; Knieriem, L.K.; Harris, M.M.; George, J.N. Platelet activation and secretion associated with emotional stress. *Circulation* **1985**, *71*, 1129–1134. [[CrossRef](#)]
310. Vidovic, A.; Grubisic-Ilic, M.; Kozaric-Kovacic, D.; Gotovac, K.; Rakos, I.; Markotic, A.; Rabatic, S.; Dekaris, D.; Sabioncello, A. Exaggerated platelet reactivity to physiological agonists in war veterans with posttraumatic stress disorder. *Psychoneuroendocrinology* **2011**, *36*, 161–172. [[CrossRef](#)]
311. Eswarappa, M.; Neylan, T.C.; Whooley, M.A.; Metzler, T.J.; Cohen, B.E. Inflammation as a predictor of disease course in posttraumatic stress disorder and depression: A prospective analysis from the Mind Your Heart Study. *Brain Behav. Immun.* **2019**, *75*, 220–227. [[CrossRef](#)]
312. Wysokinski, A.; Szczepocka, E. Platelet parameters (PLT, MPV, P-LCR) in patients with schizophrenia, unipolar depression and bipolar disorder. *Psychiatry Res.* **2016**, *237*, 238–245. [[CrossRef](#)]
313. Izzì, B.; Bonaccio, M.; de Gaetano, G.; Cerletti, C. Learning by counting blood platelets in population studies: Survey and perspective a long way after Bizzozero. *J. Thromb. Haemost.* **2018**, *16*, 1711–1721. [[CrossRef](#)]
314. Slavich, G.M.; Sacher, J. Stress, sex hormones, inflammation, and major depressive disorder: Extending Social Signal Transduction Theory of Depression to account for sex differences in mood disorders. *Psychopharmacology (Berl.)* **2019**, *236*, 3063–3079. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
315. Rožman, P.; Semenič, D.; Smrke, D.M. The Role of Platelet Gel in Regenerative Medicine. In *Advances in Regenerative Medicine*; Wislet-Gendebien, S., Ed.; IntechOpen: Rijeka, Croatia, 2011. [[CrossRef](#)]
316. Simmonds, M.J.; Watanabe, N.; Nandakumar, D.; Horobin, J. Blood-device interaction. In *Mechanical Circulatory and Respiratory Support*; Academic Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 2018; pp. 597–626. [[CrossRef](#)]
317. Bader, M. Serotonylation: Serotonin Signaling and Epigenetics. *Front. Mol. Neurosci.* **2019**, *12*, 288. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
318. Chmielewska, N.; Szyndler, J.; Maciejak, P.; Plaznik, A. Epigenetic mechanisms of stress and depression. *Psychiatr. Pol.* **2019**, *53*, 1413–1428. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
319. Howie, H.; Rijal, C.M.; Ressler, K.J. A review of epigenetic contributions to post-traumatic stress disorder. *Dialogues Clin. Neurosci.* **2019**, *21*, 417–428. [[CrossRef](#)]
320. Talarowska, M. Epigenetic Mechanisms in the Neurodevelopmental Theory of Depression. *Depress. Res. Treat.* **2020**, *2020*, 6357873. [[CrossRef](#)]

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